

Deliverable 4.2

FIRST RESULTS OF THE AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY DETECTION, DECISION & MITIGATION

Title	First Results of the AI-Driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation
Document description	This deliverable reports the initial outcomes as preliminary results coming from all the tasks in WP4, including the first analysis and design of the enablers and components for AI-driven anomaly detection, decision, and mitigation.
Nature	Public
Task	T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, and T4.4
Status	Final
WP	WP4
Lead Partner	EBOS
Partners Involved	UMU, ORO, LNVO, RHEA, EBOS, WINGS, ONE, ICT-FI, OULU, UWS
Date	27/06/2024

Revision history	Author	Delivery date	Summary of changes and comments
Version 00	EBOS	22/02/2024	Initial Table of Contents
Version 01	EBOS	29/02/2024	Agreed Table of Contents
Version 02	ALL	07/06/2024	All Sections Content Inserted by Partners
Version 03	EBOS	11/06/2024	Executive Summary, Introduction and Conclusions Inserted
Version 04	EBOS	13/06/2024	Lists of Figures, Tables, Abbreviations, References and Final Edits – Document Ready for Peer Review
Version 05	RHEA, ONE, EBOS	24/06/2024	Review corrections and comments incorporated in the document.
Version 06	OULU, UMU, RHEA, WINGS, EBOS	26/06/2024	Final corrections made by partners.
Final Version	EBOS	27/06/2024	Final version prepared and submitted to Coordinator.

Disclaimer:

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

CONTENTS

1	LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	8
2	LIST OF FIGURES	13
3	LIST OF TABLES	15
4	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	16
5	INTRODUCTION	18
5.1.	BACKGROUND	18
5.2.	OBJECTIVES	18
5.3.	ORGANIZATION OF THE DOCUMENT	18
6	AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY DETECTION	20
6.1.	INTRODUCTION	20
6.2.	PRIVACY-PRESERVING FL-BASED ANOMALY DETECTOR	21
6.2.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	21
6.2.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	22
6.2.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS	22
6.2.4.	ATTACKS TARGETED	23
6.2.5.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	23
6.3.	PRIVACY-PRESERVING FEDERATED AI FOR ANOMALY DETECTION	23
6.3.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	24
6.3.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	26
6.3.2.1.	PUBLIC DATASETS APPROACH	26
6.3.2.2.	REAL-TIME MONITORING/FLOW PROCESSING APPROACH	27
6.3.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS	27
6.3.4.	ATTACKS TARGETED	29
6.3.5.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	29
6.4.	HOLISTIC SECURITY AND PRIVACY FRAMEWORK	29
6.4.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	29
6.4.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	30
6.4.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS	31
6.4.3.1.	VALIDATION OF THE EXISTENT ML MODEL	31
6.4.3.2.	ZERO KNOWLEDGE PROOF	32
6.4.3.3.	FEDERATED LEARNING AS A SERVICE	33
6.4.4.	ATTACKS TARGETED	34
6.4.5.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	34

6.5. AI-DRIVEN CYBER-PHYSICAL CORRELATOR	35
6.5.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	35
6.5.2. DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	36
6.5.3. CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS	37
6.5.4. ATTACKS TARGETED.....	43
6.5.5. FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	43
7 AI-DRIVEN COGNITIVE DECISION MAKING.....	45
7.1. INTRODUCTION	45
7.2. AI-DRIVEN DECISION MAKING - AID.....	45
7.2.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	45
7.2.1.1. RISK ASSESSMENT MODULE OF AID	45
7.2.1.2. AI-DRIVEN AGENTS MODULE OF AID.....	46
7.2.1.3. INPUTS FOR THE AI-DRIVEN AGENTS.....	47
7.2.1.4. TRAINING OF AI DRIVEN AGENTS	47
7.2.1.5. OBJECTIVE FUNCTION USED FOR THE REWARD OF AI-DRIVEN AGENTS	48
7.2.2. DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	49
7.2.3. CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	49
7.2.4. FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	50
7.3. THREAT RISK ASSESSOR - TRA	50
7.3.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	50
7.3.2. DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	52
7.3.3. CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	52
7.3.4. FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	53
8 AI-DRIVEN SECURITY RESPONSE-MITIGATION	55
8.1. INTRODUCTION.....	55
8.2. AI-POWERED EDOS MITIGATOR.....	55
8.2.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	55
8.2.2. DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	57
8.2.3. CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	57
8.2.4. FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	59
8.3. SECURITY TESTING - DIGITAL TWINS - DT.....	60
8.3.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	60
8.3.2. DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	62
8.3.3. CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	62
8.3.4. FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	63
8.4. DYNAMIC AND AUTOMATED SERVICE COMPOSITION - DSC.....	63
8.4.1. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	63

8.4.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	64
8.4.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	64
8.4.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	67
8.5.	AI-DRIVEN 6G RESPONSE MITIGATION.....	68
8.5.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	68
8.5.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	69
8.5.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	69
8.5.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	71
8.6.	SLICING MITIGATION PLANNER SERVICE	71
8.6.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	71
8.6.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	72
8.6.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	73
8.6.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	74
9	SOAR DRIVEN NETWORK FLOW AND TOPOLOGY MONITORING.....	75
9.1.	INTRODUCTION.....	75
9.2.	NETWORK SECURITY FLOW MONITORING	75
9.2.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	75
9.2.2.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	77
9.2.3.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	79
9.3.	TOPOLOGY INVENTORY AGENT	79
9.3.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	79
9.3.2.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	80
9.3.3.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	82
10	ROBUST AND PRIVACY PRESERVING AI.....	84
10.1.	INTRODUCTION.....	84
10.2.	MTD BASED ROBUST AI.....	84
10.2.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	85
10.2.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	86
10.2.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	86
10.2.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	87
10.3.	ENCRYPTION-AS-A-SERVICE	88
10.3.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	88
10.3.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	93
10.3.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	96
10.3.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	98
10.4.	PRIVACY PRESERVING CTI SHARING - CTI	98

10.4.1.	COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE	98
10.4.2.	DATA MONITORING AND DATA SERVICES	100
10.4.3.	CURRENT PROGRESS AND INITIAL RESULTS.....	100
10.4.4.	FUTURE WORK AND RISKS	106
11	CONCLUSION	108
12	REFERENCES.....	109
13	ANNEXES.....	112

1 LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Explanation/ Definition
5G	Fifth Generation
6G	Sixth Generation
AE	AutoEncoder
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AID	AI-driven Decision Making/Engine
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
API	Application Programming Interface
AsyncFL	Asynchronous Federated Learning
B5G	Beyond 5th Generation (Networks)
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment
CICIDS2017	Canadian Institute for Cybersecurity Intrusion Detection System 2017 dataset
CNF	Cloud-Native Network Function
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPSs	Cyber-Physical Systems
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Customer Service Centre
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CTI	Cyber Threat Intelligence
CVE	Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures
CVSS	Common Vulnerability Scoring System
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
Django	A Python Web framework
DL	Deep Learning

DNN	Deep Neural Network
DNS	Domain Name System
DoS	Denial of Service
DP	Differential Privacy
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
DSC	Dynamic and Automated Service Composition
DT	Digital Twin
E1	Endpoint 1
E2	Endpoint 2
E2E	End-to-End
EDoS	Economic Denial of Sustainability
EDR	Economic Damage Repair
FL	Federated Learning
FN	Federated Node
GAT	Graph Attention Network
GENEVE	Generic Network Virtualization Encapsulation
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GRE	Generic Routing Encapsulation
GRU	Gated Recurrent Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HPA	Horizontal Pod Autoscaling
HSPF	Holistic Security and Privacy Framework
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPFlood	HyperText Transfer Protocol Flood
HTTPFlood	HyperText Transfer Protocol Flood
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

IAAS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICMPFlood	Internet Control Message Protocol Flood
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDS	Intrusion Detection System
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IIoTSET	Industrial Internet of Things Dataset
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
ITAV	Instituto de Telecomunicacoes Aveiro
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8s	Kubernetes
Kafka	Apache Kafka event streaming platform
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
M18	Month 18
M30	Month 30
MAC	Media Access Control
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MISP	Malware Information Sharing Platform
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSPL	Medium Security Policy Language
MTD	Moving Target Defence
MTU	Maximum Transmission Unit
MVC	Model-View-Controller
NFStream	A Python Network Data Analysis Framework
NFV	Network Functions Virtualization

NGINX	A Web and Proxy Server
NIDS	Network Intrusion Detection System
NMap	Network Scanner/Mapper Tool
NSFM	Network Security Flow Monitoring
Open5GS	Open-source implementation of 5G Core Network Functions
OULU	OULU University
PaySim	Payment Simulator
PET	Privacy Enhancing Technology
PostgreSQL	PostgreSQL Database
Pytorch	A machine learning library for Python
RabbitMQ	A Message Broker
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
REST API	Representational State Transfer Application Programming Interface
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
SA	Standalone (5G Core Network)
SAE	Security Analytics Engine
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SGD	Stochastic Gradient Descent
SlowrateDoS	Slow-rate Denial of Service
SMPS	Slicing Mitigation Planner Service
SO	Security Orchestrator
SOAR	Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response
SQL	Structured Query Language
STIX	Structured Threat Information eXpression
STIXv2	Structured Threat Information eXpression version 2
SyncFL	Synchronous Federated Learning

SYNFlood	SYN Packet Flood Denial-of-Service attack
SYNScan	SYN Scan attack
T4.2	Task 4.2
TIP	Threat Intelligence Platform
TRA	Threat Risk Assessor
UC	Use Case
UDPFlood	User Datagram Protocol Flood
UDPScan	User Datagram Protocol Scan
UE	User Equipment
UI	User Interface
UMU	Universidad de Murcia
UNSW-NB15	University of New South Wales Network-Based 2015 dataset
UWS	University of West Scotland
UX	User Experience
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VXLAN	Virtual Extensible LAN
WP	Work Package
WSGI	Web Server Gateway Interface
WUSTL-IIoT	Washington University in St. Louis IIoT dataset
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language
ZKP	Zero Knowledge Proof
ZTM	Zero Trust Model

Table 1. List of abbreviations and acronyms

2 LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. DATA MODEL FOR ANOMALY DETECTION REPORTS.....	20
FIGURE 2. DATA MODEL FOR ML MODEL DETAILS.....	21
FIGURE 3. HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE OF PROPOSED PRIVACY-PRESERVING FL-BASED ANOMALY DETECTOR.....	21
FIGURE 4. ACCURACY COMPARISON OF MLP-BASED ALGORITHM.....	23
FIGURE 5. FUNCTION ARCHITECTURE OF PRIVACY-PRESERVING FEDERATED AI FOR ANOMALY DETECTION (UMU).....	24
FIGURE 6. ARCHITECTURE OF THE DEEP AUTOENCODER USED IN THE ANOMALY DETECTION ENGINE.....	25
FIGURE 7. ARCHITECTURE OF THE DEEP NEURAL NETWORK USED IN THE ATTACK CLASSIFICATION ENGINE.....	26
FIGURE 8. MODEL PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR DIFFERENT TRAINING SCENARIOS.....	28
FIGURE 9. MODEL PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR EACH CLASS.....	29
FIGURE 10. HSPF COMPONENTS INTEGRATION.....	30
FIGURE 11. ZERO KNOWLEDGE PROOF INFORMATION SHARING.....	33
FIGURE 12. INTEGRATION WITH MTD ASSET.....	34
FIGURE 13. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF CYBER-PHYSICAL CORRELATOR.....	35
FIGURE 14. IMPACT OF NORMALIZATION ON SELECTED VARIABLES (A).....	38
FIGURE 15. IMPACT OF NORMALIZATION ON SELECTED VARIABLES (B).....	39
FIGURE 16. BOXPLOTS FOR FIVE DIFFERENT VARIABLES ACROSS LABELS.....	40
FIGURE 17. DATA DEPENDENCIES VISUALIZATION (A).....	40
FIGURE 18. DATA DEPENDENCIES VISUALIZATION (B).....	41
FIGURE 19. CORRELATION HEATMAP FOR BINARY CLASSIFICATION.....	41
FIGURE 20. CORRELATION HEATMAP FOR MULTI-CLASS CLASSIFICATION.....	42
FIGURE 21. AI-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING FUNCTIONAL BLOCK.....	45
FIGURE 22. EXAMPLE OF RISK ASSESSMENT MATRIX.....	46
FIGURE 23. AI-DRIVEN DECISION-MAKING FUNCTIONAL BLOCK.....	47
FIGURE 24. RISK ASSESSMENT MATRIX METHODOLOGY.....	49
FIGURE 25. PRELIMINARY RESULTS FOR THE AID FUNCTIONAL BLOCK.....	50
FIGURE 26. TRA GENERAL DESCRIPTION.....	51
FIGURE 27. STAGED RISK LEVEL ASSESSMENT.....	53
FIGURE 28. FUNCTIONAL ARCHITECTURE OF AI-POWERED EDoS MITIGATOR ASSET.....	56
FIGURE 29. THE OVERALL ARCHITECTURE OF TRAINING CG-GRU MODEL AND SELECTING THE DYNAMIC ANOMALY THRESHOLD [14].....	57
FIGURE 30. TESTBED FOR GENERATING DATASET TO TRAIN CG-GRU [15].....	58
FIGURE 31. ATTACK DETECTION PERFORMANCE OF CG-GRU [15].....	59
FIGURE 32. ECONOMIC DAMAGE CAUSED BY HULK (H) AND SLOWLORIS (S), WITH AND WITHOUT THE EDoS MITIGATOR [15].....	59
FIGURE 33. COMPONENT ARCHITECTURE FOR SMART METER – GATEWAY INTERACTION.....	60
FIGURE 34. DSC ARCHITECTURE.....	64
FIGURE 35. POLICY XML FILE TRANSLATION TO JSON.....	65
FIGURE 36. MISMATCH IDENTIFICATION AND CORRECTION.....	65
FIGURE 37. MALICIOUS ATTACK MODIFYING EXISTING SOURCEADDRESS VALUES.....	66
FIGURE 38. MISMATCH IDENTIFICATION.....	66
FIGURE 39. MISMATCH RECTIFICATION.....	67
FIGURE 40. PROVIDER AND CONSUMER EXPECTED MESSAGE SAMPLES.....	67
FIGURE 41. AI-DRIVEN RESPONSE-MITIGATOR FUNCTIONAL BLOCK.....	68
FIGURE 42. OVERALL ARCHITECTURE OF THE AI DRIVEN 6G RESPONSE MITIGATION IN CONTEXT OF RIGOROUS.....	69
FIGURE 43. EXAMPLES OF SECURITY ATTACKS IN 5G [17].....	70
FIGURE 44. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE UWS SMPS.....	72
FIGURE 45. OUTPUT EXAMPLE OF THE EXECUTION OF THE E2E QUERY OF THE SMPS.....	73
FIGURE 46. OUTPUT EXAMPLE OF SET OF MITIGATION PLANS PROVIDED BY THE SMPS.....	73
FIGURE 47. OUTPUT EXAMPLE OF THE SMPS AND MESSAGE SENT TO THE MESSAGE BUS EXCHANGE.....	74
FIGURE 48. SEQUENCE DIAGRAM OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE UWS NETWORK SECURITY FLOW MONITORING.....	76
FIGURE 49. EXAMPLE OF MULTI-LEVEL ENCAPSULATED NETWORK TRAFFIC FOR B5G NETWORKS.....	77
FIGURE 50. EXAMPLE OF UNIFIED2 LOG TO JSON FILE FOR A DDoS ALERT RAISED BY SNORT.....	78
FIGURE 51. EXAMPLE OUTPUT OF THE EXECUTED NSFM WITH THE FINE-GRAINED METADATA INFORMATION OF THE MALICIOUS NETWORK FLOW DETECTED.....	78

FIGURE 52. TIA DISTRIBUTED DEPLOYMENT	80
FIGURE 53. EXAMPLE OF TOPOLOGY INVENTORY DATABASE ENTRIES FOR NETWORK INTERFACES	81
FIGURE 54. TOPOLOGY UPDATE MESSAGE WITH NETWORK INTERFACE INFORMATION	82
FIGURE 55. TOPOLOGY UPDATE MESSAGE WITH OVS BRIDGE INFORMATION	82
FIGURE 56. ARCHITECTURE OF MTD-BASED FL	85
FIGURE 57. ACCURACY GAIN IN MTD-BASED-FL.....	87
FIGURE 58. RECOGNITION TIME IN MTD-BASED FL.....	87
FIGURE 59. DEPLOYING A DJANGO PROJECT ON KUBERNETES USING DOCKER.....	88
FIGURE 60. CONSIDERING THE SCENARIO FOR DEPLOYING THE PROJECT IN K8S	90
FIGURE 61. CONSIDERING ONE REPLICA OF POSTGRESQL ON THE SPECIFIED PORT	90
FIGURE 62. EXAMPLE SHOWS SIMPLE REQUIREMENTS FOR DJANGO	92
FIGURE 63. CONSIDERING ALLOWED HOSTS TO CONFIGURE THE FILE FOR THE ENVIRONMENT.	92
FIGURE 64. MANAGING ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES CREATING .ENV FILE AND HAVING DATABASE URLS (A)	92
FIGURE 65. THE DETAILS OF DJANGO UPSTREAM TO THE WEB SERVICE ON PORT 8000	93
FIGURE 66. THE DETAILS OF DOCKER COMPOSE UP.YML.....	93
FIGURE 67. MANAGING ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES CREATING .ENV FILE AND HAVING DATABASE URLS (B)	95
FIGURE 68. MANAGING ENVIRONMENT VARIABLES CREATING .ENV FILE AND HAVING DATABASE URLS (C)	95
FIGURE 69. THE HTTP OF THE PROJECT BASED ON STATIC VARIABLES AND TEST SERVICES WITH CURL	96
FIGURE 70. EAAS AND THE SUBSCRIPTION PART TO PREPARE TOKENS FOR NEW CLIENTS	97
FIGURE 71. FUNCTION ARCHITECTURE OF PRIVACY-PRESERVING CTI SHARING (UMU)	99
FIGURE 72. EXAMPLE OF AN ANONYMIZED EVENT IN MISP WEB INTERFACE.....	101
FIGURE 73. PRIVACY POLICY USED TO ANONYMIZE THE EVENT SHOWED IN FIGURE 70 (1)	102
FIGURE 74. PRIVACY POLICY USED TO ANONYMIZE THE EVENT SHOWED IN FIGURE 70 (2)	103
FIGURE 75. HIERARCHY POLICY USED TO ANONYMIZE THE EVENT SHOWED IN FIGURE 70 (1).....	104
FIGURE 76. HIERARCHY POLICY USED TO ANONYMIZE THE EVENT SHOWED IN FIGURE 70 (2).....	105
FIGURE 77. HIERARCHY POLICY USED TO ANONYMIZE THE EVENT SHOWED IN FIGURE 70 (3).....	106
FIGURE 78. SYSTEM MODEL DIAGRAM	112

3 LIST OF TABLES

TABLE 1. LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	12
TABLE 2. HSPF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION	32
TABLE 3. LABEL'S OPERATION AND FREQUENCY WITHIN THE REMAINING TRAIN-TEST DATASET	37
TABLE 4. BINARY AND MULTI-CLASS CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHMS.....	42
TABLE 5. BINARY CLASSIFICATION RESULTS	43
TABLE 6. MULTICLASS CLASSIFICATION RESULTS.....	43
TABLE 7. INPUTS FOR THE AI DRIVEN AGENTS	47
TABLE 8. TRA SCORES	52
TABLE 9. PROPOSED COUNTER MITIGATION ACTIONS FOR AI-ENABLED RESPONSE MITIGATION	71
TABLE 10. SYNTHETIC FRAUD TRANSACTIONS DATASET FEATURES.....	100

4 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable constitutes a continuation of deliverable D4.1 and reports the current progress of the different assets developed under WP4 up to M18. Specifically, for each asset the component architecture is detailed, relevant data monitoring and data services needed for the module to function are presented, current progress and initial results are put forward and finally future work and risks are outlined.

The assets are grouped together in five main sections based on functional relevance. The AI-Driven Anomaly Detection section delves into the assets responsible for identifying anomalies using novel privacy-preserving federated deep learning-based techniques, which aim to advance current anomaly detection methods in B5G networks. These innovations cover various areas, such as the adopted learning approaches, enhancements to federated learning aggregation procedures, and improvements in privacy protection within the federated learning framework. Several deep learning algorithms, including Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and Autoencoder, have been employed to create new anomaly detection models capable of recognizing various attacks on B5G networks and services. These models are trained on public datasets using, among other methods, a federated learning approach to promote collaborative anomaly detection.

The AI-Driven Cognitive Decision Making section provides details on the two assets that leverage the outputs of the anomaly detection modules i.e. threat classification and probability of occurrence, to provide threat impact values based on the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (the Threat Risk Assessor - TRA functional block), and calculate the overall severity level for each detected threat (the AI driven Decision Making - AID functional block). Furthermore, multiple opinions on mitigation actions are provided based on specific AI Driven Agents (AID). The results are communicated to the AI-Driven 6G Response-Mitigation module which is detailed in the corresponding section that follows along with other relevant assets.

In particular, these AI Driven Security Response-Mitigation assets include the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator which uses a Deep Learning (DL) model to identify harmful scaling requests caused by application-layer DDoS attacks, incorporating an "Admission Controller" and a "DDoS Mitigator" module. Another tool, Dynamic Automated Service Composition, detects and corrects mismatches between policies, services, and messages exchanged by IoT devices, utilizing input from the Digital Twin, which simulates IoT device communication. This simulation helps test the accuracy of mismatch detection and correction. Additionally, the AI-driven 6G response mitigation tool suggests specific mitigation actions based on detected attacks, AI Driven Decision Making suggestions and the network topology. Moreover, the Slicing Mitigation Planner Service, determines the appropriate actions and their locations within the network data plane where they will be enforced, which can include dropping traffic, redirecting it, mirroring the flow, or the enforcement of a network slice as mitigation solution.

The next section analyses the Network Flow and Topology Monitoring functional block as part of an integrated Security, Orchestration, Automation and Response (SOAR) control loop. This functional block acts as the sensing layer of the control loop, continuously monitoring the network across various domains, such as network flow and devices. The analysis of monitored resources is managed by different software components based on the use case. By isolating analysis tasks into separate components, it distributes responsibilities and computational costs effectively. For example, an

Intrusion Detection System (IDS) serves as an analysis tool, generating alerts when malicious flows are detected. These alerts provide details on the type of attack and the specific network resources impacted.

Finally, the Robust and Privacy Preserving AI section presents details on the three functional blocks that focus on securing Federated Learning through Moving Target Defence (MTD) which dynamically changes the attack surface of the system, securing data through Encryption as a Service (EaaS) and enhancing privacy through a Privacy-Preserving Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing architecture, leveraging identity and policy management, secure databases and anonymization services.

The present deliverable should be read in conjunction with D3.2 and especially the parts analysing the Trust Manager as well as the Security Orchestrator functional blocks that operate closely with the Threat Risk Assessment – TRA and the AI driven 6G Response-Mitigation functional blocks (analysed here) respectively.

The current deliverable will be followed by D4.3 on M30 (June 2025) where the final results for the assets developed in WP4 will be showcased.

5 INTRODUCTION

5.1. Background

Within WP4, the necessary assets to facilitate AI-driven anomaly detection, decision-making, and mitigation in the RIGOUROUS framework, are being developed, addressing the stringent reliability and availability requirements of 5G and B5G/6G networks and services. To achieve this, advanced Artificial Intelligence techniques such as Deep Learning, Federated Learning, and Reinforcement Learning are utilized to provide fully automated services for anomaly detection, decision-making, and mitigation.

D4.2 is considered a continuation of D4.1 which provided the initial outcomes regarding WP4 assets, in terms of state-of-the-art analysis, RIGOUROUS advancements and asset descriptions. This deliverable presents the progress regarding the WP4 assets as of M18 (June 2024) in terms of component architecture, data needed for the assets to function, current status and initial results as well as future work and risks.

5.2. Objectives

The present deliverable adheres to WP4 objectives which focus on designing and developing anomaly detection, decision-making, and mitigation mechanisms using AI. Specifically, the WP aims to:

- Develop innovative AI-powered mechanisms for federated cross-domain analytics to detect anomalies with privacy protection and resilience to adversarial attacks.
- Create dynamic and automated service composition mechanisms that combine AI with rules-based systems to identify and resolve interconnection issues (interoperability, security, privacy, and trust mismatches) among components that need to interoperate but are not pre-defined.
- Build AI-driven modules for automated decision-making to determine appropriate mitigation strategies on a case-by-case basis.
- Establish enablers for a fully functional closed control loop for automated security mitigation against cyber-attacks.

5.3. Organization of the document

The document is organised in five main sections where the corresponding assets are analysed as follows:

1. AI-Driven Anomaly Detection
 - a. Privacy-Preserving FL-Based Anomaly Detector
 - b. Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection
 - c. Holistic Security and Privacy Framework

- d. AI-Driven Cyber-Physical Correlator
- 2. AI-Driven Cognitive Decision Making
 - a. AI-Driven Decision Making – AID
 - b. Threat Risk Assessor - TRA
- 3. AI-Driven Security Response-Mitigation
 - a. AI Powered EDoS Mitigator
 - b. Security Testing – Digital Twin – DT
 - c. Dynamic and Automated Service Composition – DSC
 - d. AI-Driven 6G Response Mitigation
 - e. Slicing Mitigation Planner Service
- 4. SOAR Driven Network Flow and Topology Monitoring
 - a. Network Security Flow Monitoring
 - b. Topology Inventory Agent
- 5. Robust and Privacy Preserving AI
 - a. MTD based Robust AI
 - b. Encryption-as-a-Service
 - c. Privacy Preserving CTI Sharing

The document is complemented by corresponding lists of references, abbreviations, figures and tables.

6 AI-DRIVEN ANOMALY DETECTION

6.1. Introduction

As introduced in Section 6 of D4.1 [1], RIGOUROUS is creating a set of novel privacy-preserving federated DL-based anomaly detection assets designed to advance the existing state-of-the-art of anomaly detection methods in B5G. These advancements span different aspects, such as the learning approaches adopted, the improvements to the Federated Learning (FL) aggregation procedure, and the enhancement of privacy protection for the FL framework.

Various DL algorithms, including Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and Autoencoder, have been adopted to build new anomaly detection models capable of identifying attacks targeting 5G networks and services. The models have been trained on public datasets following a federated learning approach, allowing to foster collaborative anomaly detection. One of the developed assets (see Section 3.2) has paid a particular attention to the problem of stragglers (i.e., slow FL clients), providing a novel client selection procedure to accelerate convergence even in the presence of stragglers. Three Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) - Homomorphic Encryption, Differential Privacy, and Zero-Knowledge Proof - have been integrated into the FL-based anomaly detection assets to enhance privacy protection.

In view of facilitating interaction between the Security Analytics Engine (SAE) and the AI-driven Decision Engine (AID) in RIGOUROUS framework, unified data models have been defined for the three FL-based anomaly detection assets. The defined data models follow the standard STIX2 format. As illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2, the data models specify the format for communicating the anomaly results and the model details, respectively.

```
{
  "type": "anomaly",
  "spec_version": "2.1",
  "id": "anomaly--61f84253-fe58-4923-8566-21129a814705",
  "created": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.644603Z",
  "modified": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.644603Z",
  "flow_filename": "../eth0-collection.txt",
  "model_id": "12",
  "timestamp": "1921290190290",
  "anomalies": [
    {
      "spec_version": "2.1",
      "destination_ip": "192.168.0.2",
      "destination_port": "80",
      "created": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.644603Z",
      "flow_data": "[4, 0, 4, 0, 248, 248, 1672.74, 0]",
      "modified": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.644603Z",
      "flow_id": "1",
      "id": "anomalies--88df952e-8a89-4ad1-837d-657db68c028a",
      "label": "anomaly",
      "source_ip": "20.1.249.77",
      "revoked": false,
      "source_port": "61771",
      "type": "anomalies",
      "value": "1.45",
      "value_type": "reconstruction_error"
    },
    ...
  ]
}
```

Figure 1. Data model for anomaly detection reports.

```

{
  "type": "model",
  "spec_version": "2.1",
  "id": "model--b5708c04-ebdd-4b8e-bf95-bb52129faa24",
  "created": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.721435Z",
  "modified": "2024-04-04T20:33:29.721435Z",
  "model_id": "model1",
  "model_name": "MLP",
  "learning_type": "supervised",
  "flow_features": "['SrcPkts', 'DstPkts', 'TotPkts', 'DstBytes', 'SrcBytes', 'TotBytes', 'SrcLoad', 'DstLoad', '...']",
  "threshold": "1.20",
  "binary_class_accuracy": "99.70",
  "multi_class_accuracy": "99.70",
  "comparison_metric": "softmax",
  "framework": "tensorflow",
  "framework_version": "v0.2.1",
  "collection_tool": "nfstream",
  "collection_tool_version": "v0.6.0",
  "training_timestamp": "1921290190290"
}

```

Figure 2. Data model for ML model details.

The remaining of this section delves into the current implementation of the RIGUROUS' anomaly detection assets, presents the preliminary results obtained, and outlines the planned improvements to further develop those assets.

6.2. Privacy-Preserving FL-Based Anomaly Detector

6.2.1. Component Architecture

The current implementation of the Privacy-Preserving Federated Learning (FL)-based anomaly Detector is tailored for anomaly detection in an IIoT environment. Homomorphic Encryption (HE) is also used to enhance FL privacy by aggregating encrypted model updates. Other goals are decreasing the straggler effect in Synchronous FL (SyncFL) and communication overhead in Asynchronous FL (AsyncFL) by combining these two approaches in a new way by selecting clients to have faster convergence.

Figure 3. High-level architecture of proposed Privacy-Preserving FL-based Anomaly Detector.

The architecture in Figure 3 consists of industrial agents and aggregation server components. Industrial agents represent owners of cyber-physical systems (CPSs). A third authority generates public and private keys first. Industrial agents construct a local Deep Learning (DL) model using their own industrial CPS data, encrypt the parameters of the model using the public key, and send them to the aggregation server. The aggregation server aggregates the encrypted model parameters from each industrial agent. The aggregated encrypted parameters are then sent back to the industrial agents. The industrial agents update their DL models by decrypting the aggregated parameters with the private key. This process is repeated until the model is converged.

6.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

In this stage of implementation, only public datasets (Gas-pipeline [2] and WUSTL-IIoT [3] datasets) are being used.

The first interface is related to real-time attack detection and classification that is being simulated by reading specific datasets as CSV files (not overlapped with training and testing datasets) and sending the flow information, so the asset can read and analyze the flow (flow features, Source/Destination IP/Port, etc.), detect anomalous flows, and generate an output file in the format of STIX that includes anomaly score/name. Finally, this interface will alert the decision machine.

The second interface that is being simulated is related to the train and data model. First by receiving and setting input/parameters (such as the number of iterations, the number of clients, etc.) by the user, the interface will start to work to give information such as model ID, model name, model performance (accuracy), learning type, etc. The output of this interface will be in STIX format.

These scenarios are being deployed and tested locally in the Oulu testbed.

6.2.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The first results are being extracted from the mentioned public datasets. The original dataset has been preprocessed, normalized using the MinMaxScaler, and transformed into training and testing datasets. Afterward, they were divided among FL clients (industrial agents).

The proposed FL method was implemented in Pytorch and compared to the two FL methods: SyncFL, and AsyncFL. In addition, the Paillier Framework is used to implement HE.

Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) architecture with three fully connected layers is also used for both datasets. Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) is chosen as the optimization function, with a batch size of 64 for the Gas pipeline dataset and 1000 for the WUSTL-IIoT dataset. The learning rate and momentum are set to 0.01 and 0.8, respectively. The combination of 0.01 learning rate and 0.8 momentum produced optimal outcomes. The MLP model is evaluated using the model accuracy metric.

Figure 4. Accuracy comparison of MLP-based algorithm.

The results depicted in Figure 4 demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method in achieving higher attack detection accuracy, compared to baseline FL methods. We observe that the proposed method outperforms SyncFL, and AsyncFL in terms of accuracy by, respectively, 0.18%, and 3.53% on the Gas pipeline dataset and 0.13%, and 6.9% on the WUSTL-IIoT dataset. This is attributed to the proposed method's novel approach, which can more effectively engage straggling clients, resulting in better-predicted results.

Earlier results demonstrate the superiority of the proposed method in achieving higher attack detection accuracy compared to baseline FL methods.

6.2.4. Attacks targeted

This asset will be able to detect and generate alerts for the following types of attacks based on WUSTL-IIoT dataset [3]:

- DoS,
- Reconnaissance,
- Backdoor,
- Command injection

6.2.5. Future Work and Risks

In future work, we intend to improve the method to dynamically adapt the selection of clients at each training iteration. Also, achieve other results in terms of straggler rate, communication cost (based on model size), precision, and F1 Score.

6.3. Privacy-Preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection

6.3.1. Component Architecture

The asset architecture (see Figure 5) has been extended from the one presented in Deliverable D4.2, including the output endpoints (E1, E2) that serve the asset's information to the AI-Driven Decision Engine functional block according to the agreed data models, according to the STIXv2 format. These are:

- **E1 - Detection models information:** through a REST API, it will offer information about the models used for both the anomaly detection and the attack classification tasks. In this asset, for anomaly detection, a Deep Autoencoder is used, so information about the flow features considered for training, the accuracy obtained or the ML framework's details, among others, can be found. For attack classification, since a Deep Neural Network for multi-class classification is employed, similar information but adapted to this other type of learning is offered in the output data.
- **E2 - Real-time anomaly alerts:** through a Kafka broker and a specific topic for this purpose, the asset will publish the information of each flow detected as anomalous in real-time. For each one, identification information about the flow (source/destination IPs and ports), the attack label assigned by the Attack Classification Engine and other complementary information, such as the reconstruction error for binary classification and the confidence level for multi-class/attack classification, is specified. In addition, a reference to the models used for the detection/classification of that specific flow is included as well, so the information offered by this endpoint (E2) can be mapped to the information offered by the other endpoint (E1).

Figure 5. Function architecture of Privacy-preserving Federated AI for Anomaly Detection (UMU)

Moreover, in Figure 6, the architecture of the Deep Autoencoder used for anomaly detection is shown. Initially, the encoder consists of three fully connected layers, with each subsequent layer

having half the neurons of its predecessor. The first layer's neuron count matches the number of input features. To mitigate overfitting, a dropout layer with a 20% drop rate is included between the second and third layers, and a regularizer with a learning rate of $1e-07$ is added between the first and second layers to enhance performance. The middle section, or code layer, compresses the data to one-eighth the size of the input layer. The decoder, which mirrors the encoder, reconstructs the data at the output layer, allowing loss measurement by comparing the output to the original input data.

On the other hand, the model used for attack classification is a Deep Neural Network for multi-class classification, meaning that the input layer has as many neurons as input variables or flow features, while the output layer has as many neurons as the number of different classes or attack labels contained in the training data. The architecture of this model, which can be consulted in Figure 7, incorporates the aforementioned input and output layers as well as two dense connected layers of the same length as the input layer.

While the Deep Autoencoder for anomaly detection is trained from real-time collected data from the network, and using a Federated Learning scenario composed of several agents and an aggregator as coordinator of the process, the Deep Neural Network (DNN) used for attack classification is trained in a centralized way from a static training dataset composed of several samples/flows that correspond to various attack types. The collaboration between the two models is done through a REST API method offered by the Attack Classification Engine that allows the Anomaly Detection Engine, once it has identified one flow as anomalous, to get the attack label that correspond to that flow. This is done seamlessly and transparently, so that in the output the final result will be the anomalous flow metadata with the attack label assigned.

Figure 6. Architecture of the Deep Autoencoder used in the Anomaly Detection Engine

Figure 7. Architecture of the Deep Neural Network used in the Attack Classification Engine

6.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

6.3.2.1. Public datasets approach

This approach of leveraging publicly available datasets has been used to extract the first results. The dataset used for user-plane attacks, which are the only ones tested for the moment, is the 5G-NIDD [4]. For control-plane attacks, a dataset is being generated in UMU testbed and will be made available soon, so this asset as well as other interested partners can use it. Training and testing datasets have been created and pre-processed from the original one. Then, they were split and distributed among several FL agents so that the FL process could take place.

The real-time anomaly detection and attack classification is being simulated by a set of scripts implemented by UMU that read specific datasets for this purpose (non-overlapped with the training and testing datasets used) and send the flows information through a Kafka topic in real-time, so that the asset can read and analyse each received flow, creating an alert if a certain flow is detected as anomalous, enriched with the attack label provided by the Attack Classification Engine, and published in another topic of the same Kafka broker, that would simulate the endpoint E2. This scenario, composed of is deployed and being tested locally in UMU testbed.

This simulation environment would mimic the required capabilities of Data Monitoring and Data Services functional blocks from the perspective of anomaly detection, since these modules should make available the traffic flow-based data for training and evaluation of the implied detection models either statically (in CSV files) or dynamically (in real-time through, for instance, a Kafka topic).

6.3.2.2. Real-Time monitoring/flow processing approach

In UMU testbed, an inhouse developed real-time packet monitoring and flow processing software is used, to generate, on the one hand, datasets for model training and testing, from the capture and aggregation in flows of traffic coming from both benign and attack behaviours (simulated in the environment) and, on the other hand, to feed the Anomaly Detection Engine with real-time flow features data coming from real-time traffic monitoring.

First, the monitoring module would sniff the traffic in a certain network interface of the machine in which it is deployed, generating in real-time packet summaries with the relevant packet fields that are to be analysed. For example, IP addresses and TTL values can be extracted from the IP layer, and specific TCP flags can be extracted from the Transport layer, in case they are used. Through a Kafka topic, these summaries are sent to the flow processor module, which aggregates all the incoming packet information and generates flow statistics, which can be used to feed in real-time the detection systems with data for evaluation or the Federated Learning agents with training data. For this purpose, these flow statistics are again published by the flow processor in another Kafka topic so these consumers (detection engines, FL agents) can consume the information.

These modules would conform the Data Monitoring/Data Services functional blocks, and will be used to generate the control-plane attacks datasets and other needed datasets for this asset's evaluation, as well as to generate the real-time information to evaluate the real-time detection/alerting capabilities of the solution.

6.3.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The 5G-NIDD dataset, containing user-plane attacks and benign traffic launched against a simulated 5G environment, has been employed for the initial results. For binary classification, we configured a basic Federated Learning scenario, composed of 2 agents and an aggregator, and the Deep Autoencoder described previously is the model to be trained for 5 FL rounds and 2 local epochs per round (10 epochs in total). Two portions of the original data have been extracted and assigned to each agent. Then, each agent has divided its assigned portion into training and testing sets. The size of the training set is 40,000 samples (all from benign traffic class, unlabelled), while the size of the testing set is 13,200 samples (1/3 the size of the training set), containing an equal number of samples for benign and malign classes. Also, the model updates for each round have been obfuscated by adding Gaussian noise, and the weights are clipped to a norm of 1. These measures aim to prevent both membership inference and model poisoning attacks, respectively, and to achieve Differential Privacy during the learning procedure.

In Figure 8, some relevant model performance metrics, i.e., accuracy, recall, specificity and F1 score have been calculated for different configurations: centralized scenario (no FL, 10 epochs), FL scenario composed of 2 agents (no DP), and FL scenarios with DP and different parameters (noise multiplier, nm, and clipping norm, cn), also composed of 2 agents each. For each FL with DP scenario, the epsilon value, indicating the privacy factor achieved (calculated from the noise multiplier) is also included as "eps". As can be noted, the centralized scenario performs slightly better than the federated one, which in turn perform better than any of the FL+DP configurations. As it is logical,

the greater the noise multiplier factor is (the lower the epsilon), the more noise is added to each model update, so the performance metrics are affected since data is not in clear format. However, by doing this, we achieve privacy during the learning process, thus preventing membership inference and model poisoning attacks. The clipping norm has been fixed to a value of 1 since it is not relevant for the Differential Privacy condition. From these results, we can conclude that a good trade-off between accuracy and privacy could be the scenario with epsilon = 1. That indicates a moderate privacy, while performance metrics remain all above 95%, which guarantees a good model performance at anomaly detection.

Figure 8. Model performance metrics for different training scenarios

For multi-class/attack classification, another portion of the original 5G-NIDD dataset has been extracted. In this case, it is composed of only malign traffic samples from all the attack classes contained in the dataset, i.e., DoS/DDoS attacks: HTTPFlood, ICMPFlood, SYNflood, UDPFlood, SlowrateDoS, and scanning attacks: UDPScan, SYNScan. This sub-dataset contains a total of 213,672 samples, and is fed to the multi-class DNN employed by the Attack Classification Engine for training and testing. Again, the testing set is 1/3 the size of the training dataset. In Figure 9, the model performance metrics for each attack class, as well as the number of samples for each one (support column) are detailed. As can be seen, the results show around perfect metrics for each considered class (10 training epochs executed). Only the SlowrateDoS samples seem to be a little more difficult to be classified, but this can be due to the fact that this type of DoS aims to surpass attack detection systems by mimicking normal behaviour (not flooding the victim, as done by the other types).

```
Classification Report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

 HTTPFlood      1.00      0.99      0.99     40729
  ICMPFlood      1.00      1.00      1.00       344
   SYN Flood      1.00      1.00      1.00     2881
   SYN Scan      1.00      1.00      1.00     5960
 SlowrateDoS     0.98      1.00      0.99    21964
  UDP Flood      1.00      1.00      1.00   136906
  UDP Scan      1.00      1.00      1.00     4888

 accuracy              1.00    213672
  macro avg           1.00      1.00    213672
  weighted avg       1.00      1.00    213672
```

Figure 9. Model performance metrics for each class

6.3.4. Attacks targeted

This asset will be able to detect and generate alerts for the following types of attacks:

- User plane:
 - DoS attacks using various techniques (SYN Flood, ICMP Flood, Slowrate DoS)
 - Scanning attacks using the open-source utility NMap.
- Control plane:
 - Open5GS AMF crashing, using various techniques (e.g. CVE-2024-34476, CVE-2024-34475, CVE-2023-50019)
 - DoS attacks using various techniques (e.g., CVE-2024-33382, CVE-2022-43223)

6.3.5. Future Work and Risks

For future work, we aim to train and test the anomaly and attack classification models not only on user-plane attacks but also on control-plane attacks, so the control-plane dataset that will be generated in UMU testbed will be employed for this purpose. Also, we expect to test them with the data generated in the testbeds that this asset is to be integrated.

In addition, a more exhaustive analysis of Differential Privacy applied to the FL process has to be made, considering more noise-adding/obfuscation mechanisms apart from the Gaussian, i.e., Laplace, Laplace truncated, Uniform, etc.

Finally, larger FL deployment composed of more agents have to be tested as well. Here, the impact in model performance metrics of adding more agents (and potentially more data) to the process can be evaluated.

6.4. Holistic Security and Privacy Framework

6.4.1. Component Architecture

The Holistic Security and Privacy Framework (HSPF) framework is composed of three main components: (i) Aggregator, (ii) Collector and (iii) Agent. The Aggregator corresponds to the main framework unit, which coordinates the Federated Training procedure and performs the management and distribution of the different ML models used for anomaly detection by the different federated agents.

The Collector component collects inbound and outbound network traffic passing through the primary network interface. This information is then coupled into flows and stored until it is classified. Then, the Agent, where the federated agent resides, is responsible for inferencing the stored data, and identifying the potential malicious flow. In addition, the Agent also performs federated training rounds periodically, aiming to keep the ML model up to date being suitable to detect network traffic anomalies into the ever-changing landscape of the network communications.

The HSPF implementation architecture, present in Figure 10, illustrates how the HSPF components integrate with any application adopted to a micro-services paradigm. Moreover, the HSPF architecture has been designed to minimise potential data breaches, thus tackling the data privacy and security issue, since the collected data is never shared with any component outside of the Application Pod.

Figure 10. HSPF Components Integration

6.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The HSPF has been designed in a way that with one deployment all the services required for it to provide network anomaly detection over any Application are deployed at once. As previously mentioned, the Collector component continuously collects network traffic, which is then shared with the co-located Agent, in charge of performing the analysis of the network traffic. The data is collected from the main network interface of the Application using the NFStream tool [5] in a combination with a custom plugin, so the final set of collected features is the same than the feature vector present in the CICIDS2017 dataset [6]. Such format has been adopted considering that this dataset is one of the reference datasets commonly found in the literature for the theme of network intrusion and anomaly detection, and also considering the need for common ground to enable post-hoc performance comparison between the implemented ML approach and already existent works (that also use this feature vector).

For better understanding, the full list of features considered by the HSPF is:

```
['id', 'src_ip', 'src_port', 'dst_ip', 'dst_port', 'protocol', 'timestamp', 'udps.flow_duration', 'src2dst_packets', 'dst2src_packets', 'udps.totlen_fwd_pkts', 'udps.totlen_bwd_pkts', 'src2dst_max_ps', 'src2dst_min_ps', 'src2dst_mean_ps', 'src2dst_stddev_ps', 'dst2src_max_ps', 'dst2src_min_ps', 'dst2src_mean_ps', 'dst2src_stddev_ps', 'udps.flow_byts_s', 'udps.flow_pkts_s', 'udps.flow_iat_max', 'udps.flow_iat_mean', 'udps.flow_iat_min', 'udps.flow_iat_std', 'udps.fwd_iat_tot', 'src2dst_mean_piat_ms', 'src2dst_stddev_piat_ms', 'src2dst_max_piat_ms', 'src2dst_min_piat_ms', 'udps.bwd_iat_tot', 'dst2src_mean_piat_ms', 'dst2src_stddev_piat_ms', 'dst2src_max_piat_ms', 'dst2src_min_piat_ms', 'src2dst_psh_packets', 'dst2src_psh_packets', 'src2dst_urg_packets', 'dst2src_urg_packets', 'udps.fwd_header_len', 'udps.bwd_header_len', 'udps.fwd_pkts_s', 'udps.bwd_pkts_s', 'udps.pkt_len_min', 'udps.pkt_len_max', 'udps.pkt_len_mean', 'udps.pkt_len_std', 'udps.pkt_len_var', 'udps.fin_flag_cnt', 'udps.syn_flag_cnt', 'udps.rst_flag_cnt', 'udps.psh_flag_cnt', 'udps.ack_flag_cnt', 'udps.urg_flag_cnt', 'udps.cwe_flag_cnt', 'udps.ece_flag_cnt', 'udps.down_up_ratio', 'udps.pkt_size_avg', 'udps.fwd_seg_size_avg', 'udps.bwd_seg_size_avg', 'udps.fwd_byts_b_avg', 'udps.fwd_pkts_b_avg', 'udps.fwd_blk_rate_avg', 'udps.bwd_byts_b_avg', 'udps.bwd_pkts_b_avg', 'udps.bwd_blk_rate_avg', 'udps.subflow_fwd_pkts', 'udps.subflow_fwd_byts', 'udps.subflow_bwd_pkts', 'udps.subflow_bwd_byts', 'udps.init_fwd_win_byts', 'udps.init_bwd_win_byts', 'udps.fwd_act_data_pkts', 'udps.fwd_seg_size_min', 'udps.active_mean', 'udps.active_std', 'udps.active_max', 'udps.active_min', 'udps.idle_mean', 'udps.idle_std', 'udps.idle_max', 'udps.idle_min', 'bidirectional_packets']
```

6.4.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The latest developments of the HSPF components focused on validating the different architectural blocks, namely on extensively validate the existent ML model. In addition, an initial implementation of Zero Knowledge Proof (ZKP) has been completed, as well as the development of a dedicated API for the integration between the HSPF and the MTD (detailed in Section 10.2).

6.4.3.1. Validation of the existent ML model

To evaluate the performance of the HSPF detection module, the HSPF has been deployed next to the Mobitrust platform [7], a micro-services oriented application, where normal traffic was generated, collected, classified and used to train the autoencoder applied by the HSPF detection module.

Three types of attacks were simulated against the Mobitrust services: DDOS, Brute Force and SQL Injection. The first was conducted with the `mqtt-stresser` [8] tool and targeted the message-broker component, whilst the second and the third both targeted the `mt-gateway` component and were conducted with `curl` [9], recurring to a set of most common usernames and passwords, as well as to recurring commands attempted during SQL Injection.

Table 2 presents the results obtained by the HSPF detection module. The *sensitivity* achieved for the targeted components, message-broker and gateway, were of 95.83% and 100.00%. As for the remaining components, the detection mechanism correctly classified 93.35%, 87.62% and 87.64% of normal flows for the monitor, orchestrator and postgresql components, respectively.

Component	TP	TN	FP	FN
Gateway	2646	28640	4562	115
Message-Broker	4083	36046	3164	0
Monitor	0	17856	1274	0
Orchestrator	0	29961	3710	0
Postgresql	0	40237	5675	0

Table 2. HSPF performance evaluation

6.4.3.2. Zero Knowledge Proof

An authentication method based on Zero Knowledge Proof (ZKP) is being developed to increase data security. This method allows two components (Aggregator and Agent) to share information without revealing its content, thus increasing data privacy and security throughout training rounds. With this method, the Aggregator and the Agent components can prove each other that are trusted and they are the same component all the time, by sending proof in each message. If the aggregator doesn't have an agent's signature, this agent doesn't start the federated training and can't send any more messages to Aggregator.

Figure 11. Zero Knowledge Proof Information Sharing

6.4.3.3. Federated Learning as a Service

For the integration with the MTD asset (present in Figure 12), a dedicated service was developed, which consists of an API that provides the characteristics of a federated approach from an aggregation point of view. In detail, this API provides endpoints supporting the following actions: (i) receive and aggregate model weights from different federated clients; (ii) download the aggregated model.

Moreover, the data provider functionality has also been incorporated into the HSPF components, also in the form of an API, which provides the following capabilities: (i) retrieve number of features; (ii) retrieve training data; (iii) retrieve testing data.

Considering the preliminary stage of this integration, the validation and testing phase, including their respective outcomes will be further described in deliverable D4.3 on M30, which will present the final results of WP4 on AI-driven anomaly detection, decision and mitigation.

Figure 12. Integration with MTD Asset

6.4.4. Attacks Targeted

HSPF will be trained to detect and generate alerts for different kind of attacks. This training through datasets and simulated environments relates to attacks such as:

- DoS Hulk, DoS. DoS Slowloris, DoS Slowhttptest, DDoS;
- Scanning attacks, using the open-source utility Nmap;
- FTP-Patator, SSH-Patator;
- Bot, Brute Force, Web Attack, SQL Injections

6.4.5. Future Work and Risks

A new model capable of identifying different types of attacks is being studied, presenting a considerable evolution from the existing binary approach towards a multi-class one. Exploratory work is being conducted to assess the feasibility of different models to obtain the most suitable approach. To identify such an approach, we aim to consider the model's ability to identify different types of attacks, the number of false positives, and the required training time.

Moreover, the investigation and implementation of PETs into the HSPF mechanisms will continue to be pursued, namely with a focus on Differential Privacy, which aims to increase the existent data privacy level in FL, and to increase the trust level between the different federated parties.

6.5. AI-Driven Cyber-Physical Correlator

6.5.1. Component Architecture

Cyber Physical Correlator can identify anomalies by understanding changes in the distribution of transmitted data. One big advantage of the tool is that it can correlate events from heterogeneous sources. For the RIGOUROUS project, the main focus will be to use Cyber Physical Correlator in order to detect intrusions in the computer network. In order to train the tool, we will use UNSW-NB 15 and Edge IIoTSET datasets. Cyber Physical Correlator will be able to detect attacks in the network like DoS/DDoS attacks, Information gathering, Man in the middle attacks, Injection attacks, and Malware attacks. Correlator can correlate anomalies in the network with abnormal situations detected by sensors in the field and in that way to have better accuracy and decrease false alerts.

Figure 13 shows the general architecture of the solution. The connected devices send messages to a Kafka broker. Then, the messages are consumed, and the information is stored in a database. Correlator reads the information and makes predictions using Machine Learning algorithms. In case an anomaly is detected, the user is informed by an alert message that is shown in the dashboard.

Figure 13. Functional architecture of Cyber-Physical Correlator

6.5.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

For the model training the UNSW-NB15 dataset was used. The dataset consists of a majority of benign flows (87.35%) and a smaller portion of attack flows (12.65%). For benchmarking purposes, a specific subset of this data is used, including 175,341 instances for training and 82,332 for testing, covering 9 different types of anomalies and normal flows. The challenge lies in accurately detecting and classifying the less frequent but potentially more damaging attack types.

The chosen benchmark dataset is considered the most representative publicly available option, encompassing diverse and accurately labelled malicious patterns. However, the limited number of instances for each class, mirroring real-world scenarios, creates a highly imbalanced learning environment. Table 3 offers details on each label's operation and frequency within the remaining train-test dataset, after removing instances with missing values.

Regarding feature engineering, the initial dataset contained various types of features (nominal, integer, binary, float), along with two timestamp-related features, which were removed due to redundancy.

Class / Label	Count	Train/Test split	Description
Normal	1550712	19,488 / 9,625	Normal unmalicious flows
Fuzzers	19463	1,731/ 535	The attacker sends large amounts of random data which cause a system to crash and aims to discover security vulnerabilities in a system.
Analysis	1995	564 / 0	A group that presents a variety of threats that target web applications through ports, emails, and scripts.
Backdoor	1782	99 / 11	A technique that aims to bypass security mechanisms by replying to specific constructed client applications.
DoS	5051	1,791 / 717	Denial of Service is an attempt to overload a computer system's resources with the aim of preventing access to or availability of its data.
Exploits	24736	16,187 / 5,293	Are sequences of commands controlling the behaviour of a host through a known vulnerability.

Generic	5570	39,496 / 18,460	A method that targets cryptography and causes a collision with each block-cipher.
Reconnaissance	12291	1,703 / 504	A technique for gathering information about a network host and is also known as a probe.
Shellcode	1365	0 / 0	A malware that penetrates a code to control a victim's host.
Worms	153	114 / 34	Attacks that replicate themselves and spread to other computers.

Table 3. Label's operation and frequency within the remaining train-test dataset

6.5.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The analysis began by converting nominal features ('proto', 'service', 'state') into numerical representations using one-hot encoding, resulting in 60 real-valued variables. This transformation facilitates compatibility with most machine learning algorithms. Subsequently, robust scaling was applied to normalize these variables and prevent overfitting, a choice validated through the analysis process. This method, unlike min-max normalization or standardization, adjusts scaling based on each variable's quantile range, making it less susceptible to outliers. Figure 14 and Figure 15 illustrate the impact of normalization on selected variables.

Figure 14. Impact of normalization on selected variables (a)

Figure 15. Impact of normalization on selected variables (b)

Despite normalization, machine learning models remained vulnerable to issues caused by redundant or misleading variables. To address this, variable correlation with the corresponding label was examined. Prior to feature selection and further analysis, the data was explored using descriptive statistics and plots to identify patterns or behaviours within the existing classes.

Figure 16 displays boxplots for five different variables across labels, revealing similarities among most malicious labels and distinguishing the 'Normal' label. The presence of numerous outliers underscores the complexity of the problem. This observation led to the division of the learning pipeline into two stages: first, classifying flows as 'Normal' or 'Attack,' followed by identifying the specific category of 'Attack' flows. This approach offers greater flexibility in fine-tuning the mechanisms.

Figure 16. Boxplots for five different variables across labels

To validate this assumption, dimensionality reduction using uMAP was employed to visualize dependencies within the data. Figure 17 and Figure 18 illustrate representative cases.

Figure 17. Data Dependencies Visualization (a)

Figure 18. Data Dependencies Visualization (b)

Feature selection was performed for both stages to eliminate detrimental variables. Correlation between each variable and the class variable was calculated, retaining the most informative ones based on predefined thresholds. For the binary and multi-class classification stages, thresholds of 0.20 and 0.30 were set, respectively, resulting in feature spaces of 14 and 15 dimensions. Figure 19 and Figure 20 display heatmaps of these correlations.

Figure 19. Correlation Heatmap for Binary Classification

Figure 20. Correlation Heatmap for Multi-Class Classification

Finally, classification algorithms were applied to both stages, aiming to maximize the f1-score for the binary classification and balance accuracy and macro-averaged f1-score for the multi-class classification. Various algorithms were explored, with ensemble learners based on decision trees demonstrating the most promising performance, striking a balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.

Scenario	Binary	Multi-class
Stage	1st	2 nd
Classification model	Random forest	Extra Trees
Feature space	Augmented with deep feature synthesis without PCA	Augmented with deep feature synthesis with PCA
Parameters	Splitting criterio: entropy Max_depth: 14 Class_weight: balanced N_estimators: 75	Splitting criterio: entropy Max_depth: 12 Class_weight: balanced N_estimators: 50

Table 4. Binary and Multi-class Classification Algorithms

Actual / Predicted	Attack	Normal
Attack	25471	83
Normal	998	8627
f1-score	0.979 (Positive label: Attack)	

Table 5. Binary Classification Results

Actual / Predicted	Backdoor	DoS	Exploits	Fuzzers	Generic	Reconnaissance	Worms
Backdoor	0	1	7	1	0	2	0
DoS	1	54	433	21	25	178	5
Exploits	0	212	3902	207	30	915	27
Fuzzers	0	8	384	50	17	75	1
Generic	0	13	211	8	18161	66	1
Reconnaissance	0	30	286	19	7	159	3
Worms	0	1	16	2	0	14	1
f1-score	0.31 (averaged at macro-level)						

Table 6. Multiclass Classification Results

The results highlight the effectiveness of detecting less frequent, potentially more harmful classes, even if their detection rate isn't high. Misclassifying rare instances into other harmful categories can still trigger valuable alerts. Overlap between 'Reconnaissance' and 'Exploits' instances, as we can see in Figure 18, indicates the difficulty of differentiating them. The inability to classify any 'Backdoor' instances is attributed to the scarcity of data in that class.

6.5.4. Attacks targeted

Cyber-Physical Correlator's main focus will be to detect the following types of attacks:

- DoS,
- Reconnaissance,
- Backdoor,
- Man in the Middle,
- False Data Injection

6.5.5. Future Work and Risks

The next step to develop a new model that will be capable of identifying additional types of attacks. In order to train the new model, it is necessary to identify additional datasets that contain more classes of cyberattacks.

Moreover, when the development of the ML model is finalized, we will use data from WINGS' testbed in order to validate the accuracy of the tool.

7 AI-DRIVEN COGNITIVE DECISION MAKING

7.1. Introduction

The current section details the architecture, functionality and progress of the two assets being developed under T4.2 that contribute to the threat decision-making process of the RIGOUROUS framework, namely the AI-driven Decision Making – AID and the Threat Risk Assessor – TRA. TRA provides AID the impact values for each detected threat and AID decides the overall risk severity level of the threat, by taking also into consideration, the probability of occurrence of the threat. AID then utilizes AI driven agents to produce multiple opinions regarding threat mitigation actions that will in turn be communicated to AI-Response/Mitigation module (see next section) for the selection of a definitive mitigation policy.

7.2. AI-driven Decision Making - AID

7.2.1. Component Architecture

7.2.1.1. Risk Assessment Module of AID

Figure 21 shows the component architecture of the AI-driven Decision-making (AID) module. The input to the functional block is the threat ID and the threat probability that would be acting as an input to the AID functional block. Using this information along with the risk scores forwarded by the Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) the AID is going to compute a threat risk assessment matrix for the decision purposes. The risk assessment matrix is computed by the AID as explained in the following section.

Figure 21. AI-driven decision-making functional block

Figure 22. Example of Risk Assessment Matrix

The AID calculates the initial risk assessment matrix of potential threats and assess their severity. Figure 22 shows an example of a Risk Assessment Matrix, with the horizontal axis using the severity level of risks, spanning from minor to major or potentially "catastrophic," depending on the chosen scale. The vertical axis uses the probability level or likelihood of the risks, ranging from improbable to highly probable or certain.

The risk assessment matrix is calculated in the following steps:

1. Enumerating the threats present within the framework by taking the input from the respective machine learning classifiers. The machine learning classifier provides the probability value of each classification and label of the threat.
2. The Threat Risk Assessor (TRA) provides the impact values for each detected threat type.
3. Merging the likelihood in terms of the probability that is provided by each machine learning classifier and impact values provided by TRA to create a risk assessment matrix.
4. Assigning severity levels (green, yellow, orange, or red) and the likelihood of occurrence (unlikely or very likely) to each risk.

7.2.1.2. AI-Driven Agents Module of AID

Figure 23 shows the component architecture of the AI-driven Decision-making (AID) module. It uses multiple AI models (agents) that uses the reinforcement learning techniques. One of these agents would be optimized for the time and the other agent would be optimized for the risk factor reduction. A reward function, action and state space of the agents will be used to train and give decisions accordingly.

Figure 23. AI-driven decision-making functional block

7.2.1.3. Inputs for the AI-Driven Agents

The inputs for training the AI-driven agents are mentioned in Table 7. The initial risk values related to each attack on the network is received as an input from TRA. The fields 3,4,5,6 and 7 as mentioned in Table 7 correspond to the hyperparameters of the AI-Driven agents.

S.No.	Input Symbol	Description of the Input
1.	N	Number of Nodes of the Network
2.	A	Number of attacks on the network at a certain instance
3.	C	Number of the counter mitigation actions. A description related to each counter mitigation action is explained in the Table 9.
4.	$T, E, \$$	Time, Energy and Monetary cost related to each counter mitigation action [0, 10]. This cost would be used in Q table for minimizing the objective functions of the AI agents
5.	M	Percentage of safety limit. It is used to calculate the stopping criteria for the training process of AI agents
6.	ξ	Limit of monetary budget
7.	X	Minimum risk factor reduction for the iterations.
8.	R	The initial risk values related to attacks on the network.

Table 7. Inputs for the AI Driven Agents

7.2.1.4. Training of AI Driven Agents

This section explains the policy decisions that are going to be produced by agent 1 and agent 2 respectively. Both AI driven agents are going to do the policy decisions using the reinforcement

learning technique named Q-learning. The goal of the agents would be to maximize the cumulative reward over time by interacting with its surroundings. The expected cumulative rewards that the agents can obtain in a particular state by executing a particular action are represented by the Q-value. The Q-values are stored in each state by using a table, often known as the Q-table. At the beginning, the agent acts randomly and the Q-table is empty. The Q-values are updated by the agents based on observable rewards and transitions, as it explores the environment. Based on the reward function, agent 1 would be optimized for the time. Agent 2 would be optimized to make the policy decisions based on optimizing the risk reduction.

The main steps for the Q-learning algorithm are given below that would be used for both the agents:

1. Initialize the Q-table with zeros or random values.
2. Observe the current state.
3. Using an exploration-exploitation strategy, such as epsilon greedy choose an action.

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_{\min} + (\epsilon_{\max} - \epsilon_{\min}) * e^{-\text{decay} * \text{epoch}}$$

4. Take the chosen action, receive a reward, and transition to the next state.
5. Update the Q-value of the current state-action pair using the Q-learning update rule:

$$Q(s, a) = Q(s, a) + lr * (R(s, s') + \gamma * \max(Q(s', a')) - Q(s, a))$$

Where,

$Q(s, a)$ is the Q-value of state s and action a .

lr is the learning rate that controls the impact of new information.

$R(s, s')$ is the reward received for taking action a in state s .

γ (gamma) is the discount factor that balances immediate and future rewards.

$\max(Q(s', a'))$ is the maximum Q-value over all possible actions in the next state s' .

Until the agent has adequately explored the environment and the Q-values have converged to their ideal values, the process of updating Q-values and choosing actions will continue. After learning is finished, the agent can choose the action in each state that has the highest Q-value to follow the learnt policy.

7.2.1.5. Objective Function used for the Reward of AI-Driven Agents

The objective function that is used to calculate the objective function of the AI-driven agents is given in the equation below.

$$J = \sum_{\forall \theta_c \in \mathcal{L}} \frac{\text{Current Risk Value}}{\beta_1 T^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c) + \beta_2 E^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c) + \beta_3 \Psi^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)}$$

The denominator of the objective function gives the total cost associated where $T^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost related to time, $E^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost associated to the energy and $\Psi^{\text{tot}}(\theta_c)$ denotes the total cost associated with the monetary costs for each iteration of the agent.

The numerator of the function denotes the safety of the network by calculating the Risk Value and

Current Risk Value. The risk value is the maximum possible risk factor reduction if all of the attacks are addressed. The Current Risk value gives the reduction in the risk that are resulted from the applied countermeasures. It is calculated after the agent selects an action. The β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are weighting values associated with each cost. These would be selected according to the needs of the agent's objective function.

7.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The information from the multi-class classifiers is communicated in the format of Structured Threat Information Expression (STIX). STIX is a language and serialisation format used to exchange Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI). STIX enables to share CTI in a consistent and machine-readable manner from the multi-class classifiers. When a threat is detected the AID as well as TRA are initiated via KAFKA bus. The AID then computes the risk assessment matrix against the threat reported by multi class classifiers and their risk values as reported by TRA.

7.2.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

Figure 24. Risk Assessment Matrix Methodology

A machine learning code is developed at the current stage taking the inputs and computing the risk assessment matrix as shown in the Figure 24 and the output is shown in Figure 25. A communication mechanism is established with the TRA so that the risk scores are forwarded to AID and the AID communicates and decides the threat to be either preventive, directive or corrective. These decisions are then going to be forwarded to AI-driven 6G Response Mitigation.

Figure 25. Preliminary Results for the AID Functional Block

7.2.4. Future Work and Risks

The future work would look into the initial results, that would be produced by completing the computational loop of receiving the threat notification from the respective multi-class classifiers and the risk scores from the TRA. Also, the AI driven agents would be designed according to the objective function as well as the weighting functions to give the policy decisions to risk mitigator.

7.3. Threat Risk Assessor - TRA

7.3.1. Component Architecture

Figure 26. TRA General Description

As depicted in Figure 26, the Threat Risk Assessor [TRA] service receives the **{Threat Notification}** information from the [AID], fetches contextual and threat information from the fabric **{CTI, System Model}** to assess the actual Level of Risk based using Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) and contextual mitigation factors provided by external services such as the [ZTM]. The points below provide high level information regarding the relevant key topics associated with the bold and bracketed terms:

- [TRA] receives the Threat notification from the AID from a dedicated REST API interface.
- [TRA] receives either from RIGOUROUS fabric or from external resource(s) the characteristics (HW, SW, operation etc.) of the [ASSET] or [RESOURCE] targeted by the attack notified by the AID or potentially compromised during its execution.
 - The structured **{System Model}** characterises assets or resources (see Annex 1) including:
 - End user device, application or resource hardware and software description,
 - Network interfaces characterisation,
 - User information (authentication credential, access level, capabilities etc.),
 - Connections and flow definition,
 - Refer to system-model (.json) in Annex 1, for a complete description.
 - The completeness of the targeted asset or resource characterisation is a best effort service, expected information may not be available to fabric.
 - The TRA shall also rely on default backup parameters when one or more field of the system model is not defined,
 - The TRA shall provide a risk score even when the targeted asset/resource is unknown or not fully characterised through the system model (see Annex 1).
- The contextual **{Cyber Threat Intelligence}** knowledge (threat definition, CTI, Common vulnerability databases etc.) is retrieved from a publish/subscribe messaging service instantiated by RIGOUROUS framework (Kafka). Alternatively, it can be retrieved from external vulnerability repositories such as:
 - The NIST National Vulnerability Data Base [10]
 - The MITRE Common Vulnerability & Exposure [11]
- Given the **{Cyber Threat Intelligence}** (threat identification, threat type) and the exploitable vulnerabilities corresponding to the **{System Model}** of the asset or resource under attack, the [TRA] establishes the potential impact (severity) of the Threat.
- The impact (severity) result also considers the current Trust posture of the information queried from the ZTM to establish the current Trust posture the asset or resource under threat or potentially compromised.
- The [TRA] processes the information and returns to the AID a level of risk = {Risk Score} as per the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS).
 - TRA shall support Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) V3.1 as baseline [12]
 - TRA extended capability should support Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) V4.0 [13]
- Alternatively, the [TRA] processes the information and returns to the AID a level of risk = {Risk Score} using qualitative or semi-Quantitative risk scale as shown in Table 8.

Level of Threat	Threat Risk Assessor Criticality criteria				
	No Impact	Any other Security loss	Major Degradation	Mission Loss	Mission Loss + Propagation (data exfiltration)
	<i>level 1</i>	<i>level 2</i>	<i>level 3</i>	<i>level 4</i>	<i>level 5</i>
Very High <i>level 5</i>	Acceptable score: 5	Acceptable score: 10	Unacceptable score: 15	Unacceptable score: 20	Unacceptable score: 25
High <i>level 4</i>	Acceptable score: 4	Acceptable score: 8	Unacceptable score: 12	Unacceptable score: 16	Unacceptable score: 20
Moderate <i>level 3</i>	Acceptable score: 3	Acceptable score: 6	Acceptable score: 9	Unacceptable score: 12	Unacceptable score: 15
Low <i>level 2</i>	Acceptable score: 2	Acceptable score: 4	Acceptable score: 6	Acceptable score: 8	Unacceptable score: 10
Extremely Low <i>level 1</i>	Acceptable score: 1	Acceptable score: 2	Acceptable score: 3	Acceptable score: 4	Acceptable score: 5

Table 8. TRA Scores

7.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

As part of the AI-driven attack cognitive decision-making, orchestration and management function, the AID sends a **Risk Assessment Request** to the TRA when a detected anomaly has been identified as a threat. The AID should post directly over a dedicated REST interface the Assessment Request message with necessary metrics and potential metadata to characterise the threat which has been detected.

Upon receipt of the threat notification from the AID, the TRA uses the messaging service available on RIGOUROUS fabric to retrieve the Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) data correlated to the ongoing threat. As baseline, RIGOUROUS messaging service is provided by an Apache Kafka broker for real-time publish/subscribe services, thereby ensuring the immediate update of threat intelligence from CTI servers and other data providers (e.g. SIEM, anomaly detectors etc.).

The exchange of CTI data between the AID and the TRA should adhere to robust industry standards such as Structured Threat Information Expression (STIX2), which is a language and serialization format used to exchange CTI across organizations in a consistent and machine-readable manner, allowing security communities to better understand what computer-based attacks they are most likely to see and to anticipate and/or respond to those attacks faster and more effectively.

7.3.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The continual enhancement of the TRA involves its evolving ability to establish diverse connections and communicate efficiently with the intended system to extract specific information. This process aids in integrating and fostering interaction within the testing environment.

In essence, the TRA operates on a server-client framework where the server actively awaits connections, handles incoming client requests, retrieves data from a Kafka topic, and then transmits responses containing the extracted data and random risk score back to the clients via the desired communication channel API or Socket.

7.3.4. Future Work and Risks

As shown in Figure 27, the initial vector attack initiates a threat cascade through various network components (Asset 1, Asset J, and the Targeted Asset), each of which has its own set of vulnerabilities that are assessed successively by the TRA.

The TRA's future work will be focused on determining the individual risk level (IRL) for each asset based on the severity of its specific vulnerabilities, categorized as high, medium, or low. This assessment will consider the potential impact of a threat on an asset, solely in terms of the asset's vulnerabilities, without accounting for its interactions or dependencies with other resources.

Subsequently, these IRLs will be fed into the Security Orchestrator (SO), which will then analyse the aggregate risk in order to calculate the Cumulative Risk Level (CRL). This level characterizes the impact of a threat on a targeted asset or resource as a result of the exploitation of one or more vulnerabilities affecting one or more assets along the attack path, from the entry point to the actual targeted resource.

This will result in the implementation of a strategic mitigation response that addresses both the specific vulnerabilities and the broader network impact.

Figure 27. Staged Risk Level Assessment

With regard to the risks, several open points remain that require further clarification and discussion with project partners and stakeholders. These include finalizing the specifics of data sharing protocols, refining the server-client communication processes, and ensuring the seamless interoperability of all system components within the broader RIGOUROUS project environment.

8 AI-DRIVEN SECURITY RESPONSE-MITIGATION

8.1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) has transformed our lives, connecting everyday devices and enabling smart homes, cities, and industries. However, this interconnectedness also exposes a vast attack surface for cybercriminals, making IoT devices a prime target for exploitation. Traditional cybersecurity measures often fall short in addressing the unique challenges posed by IoT. This is where Artificial Intelligence (AI) emerges as a game-changer, revolutionizing the way we respond to and mitigate cyberattacks in IoT environments. IoT devices are often riddled with vulnerabilities due to their limited processing power, insecure software, and weak authentication mechanisms. Cyber attackers exploit these weaknesses to gain unauthorized access, steal sensitive data, disrupt operations, or even cause physical harm. The sheer number and diversity of IoT devices make manual monitoring and response impractical. This is where AI steps in, offering a scalable and intelligent solution to bolster IoT cybersecurity. AI-powered tools can automate incident response workflows, accelerating the time it takes to contain and mitigate cyberattacks. By correlating alerts, prioritizing incidents, and triggering predefined actions, these tools can reduce the burden on security teams and minimize the impact of attacks. Additionally, AI tools can integrate threat intelligence feeds from various sources, providing real-time insights into emerging threats and vulnerabilities. This enables organizations to proactively patch vulnerabilities, update security policies, and educate users about potential risks.

In RIGOROUS project, several tools based on AI will be developed to enhance mitigation of cyberattacks. AI-powered EDoS Mitigator proactively combats Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attacks. It achieves this by employing a Deep Learning (DL) forecasting model to identify harmful scaling requests triggered by application-layer DDoS attacks. This mitigation system comprises two main elements, the "Admission Controller" and the "DDoS Mitigator" module. Another tool which focuses in mitigation is Dynamic Automated Service Composition, which is able to detect mismatches between policies, services and messages exchanged by IoT devices. In case of inconsistencies or errors are found, the tool automatically proposes corrections. Dynamic Automated Service Composition receives input from the Digital Twin, which simulates the communication between IoT devices like smart meters with the gateway and the server. This topology can be used in order to test the accuracy of the detected mismatches and the correctness of the proposed corrections. Finally, the AI driven 6G response mitigation proposes specific mitigation actions, based on the detected attacks and the network topology.

8.2. AI-powered EDoS Mitigator

8.2.1. Component Architecture

Figure 28. Functional architecture of AI-powered EDoS Mitigator asset

As introduced in Deliverable D4.1, the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator can proactively mitigate Economical Denial of Sustainability (EDoS) attacks by adopting a Deep Learning (DL)-powered forecasting-based approach for detecting malicious scaling requests caused by application-layer DDoS attacks. The key components of the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator, as illustrated in Figure 28, are the “Admission Controller” and the “DDoS Mitigator” module [14] [15]:

- **Admission Controller** is in charge of intercepting the scaling-up/out requests triggered by the Auto-scaling Module of the cloud-native platform in order to entrust the scaling decision to the DDoS Mitigator for validation.
- **DDoS Mitigator** exploits the potential of DL to automatically discriminate malicious scaling requests engendered by application-layer DDoS attacks from those caused by legitimate load. It includes a DL-based anomaly detection model which can effectively identify anomalous Virtual Network Function (VNF) metrics using a data-driven forecasting-based approach. Indeed, the anomalies are detected when the predicted metrics’ values drift considerably from the observed ones. If an anomaly is identified, the scaling operation is flagged as malicious and will be refused by the Admission Controller.

Figure 29 illustrates the overall architecture of the proposed DL-based forecasting model, dubbed CG- GRU. It is an hybrid model that combines the advantages of different deep neural network algorithms, specifically Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), Graph Neural Network (GNN), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP), to provide both feature extraction and forecasting capabilities. The feature extraction stage consists in capturing both temporal and spatial dependencies within the multivariate time series using CNN, GNN (specifically Graph Attention), and RNN (specifically Gated Recurrent Unit - GRU). The forecasting stage takes the spatio-temporal representations learned by the feature extraction block as inputs to predict the future VNF’s metrics values using MLP. To set an appropriate threshold for detecting malicious VNF scaling requests, we adopt a dynamic thresholding methodology. This method allows to calculate an anomaly detection threshold that is automatically adjusted according to the past smoothed forecasting errors. For further details on the proposed model and the selection of the anomaly threshold, please refer to [14] [15].

Details on the current implementation of the asset will be provided in the subsequent sections.

Figure 29. The overall architecture of training CG-GRU model and selecting the dynamic anomaly threshold [14]

8.2.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

To collect data that can be used by the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator for training or during serving time, we implemented a “Monitoring System” that uses Prometheus API and different probes to extract the raw resource usage (e.g., CPU, memory, disk and network usage) and performance (e.g., response time) metrics from the virtual Content Delivery Network (vCDN) slices’ Cloud Native Functions (i.e., video streamer and cache) and their hosting nodes. To this end, Prometheus relies on different monitoring probes, including NGINX-to-Prometheus log file exporter [16], cadvisor [17] and node-exporter [18].

The metrics are collected as time series and returned in a CSV file. The Monitoring System offers the capabilities to generate on-demand dataset for training and testing the DL model or continuously scrape the metrics values to be consumed by the trained DL model integrated in DDoS Mitigator for real-time forecasting-based anomaly detection. The collected data are also used to drive the resource scaling decisions made by the auto-scaling module.

8.2.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

Due to the lack of real data, we built a testbed based on a Kubernetes (K8s) cluster set up on OULU’s CSC OpenStack-based cloud (<https://research.csc.fi/>) to generate realistic datasets to train and test the proposed anomaly detection approach. As illustrated in Figure 30, Open5GS [19] and UERAN-SIM [20] are used to implement the 5G SA Core and simulate the 5G RAN and User Equipment (UEs), respectively. The simulated UEs are used to generate normal or malicious load.

The raw resource usage and performance metrics data were recorded from two vCDN slices over a period of 5 days. The training data were collected during the first 4 days of attack-free activity. The 5th day served to create the testing dataset where application-layer DDoS attacks were executed on different periods of the day. Specifically, three Hulk attacks with different intensities and one Slowloris attack were launched. During training, 20% of samples in the training dataset are used for validation.

To promote reproducibility and support independent investigations beyond this study, we have made the generated dataset publicly accessible (<https://zenodo.org/records/8111592>). More details on the testbed, the dataset generation procedure, the model's hyperparameter tuning and training processes can be found in [14] [15].

Figure 30. Testbed for generating dataset to train CG-GRU [15]

We assessed the effectiveness of AI-powered EDoS Mitigator in preventing fraudulent resource scaling requests by measuring the performance of CG-GRU model in detecting application-layer DDoS attacks over the testing dataset using Precision, Recall (a.k.a. sensitivity) and F1-score metrics. We compared CG-GRU with the LSTM-based anomaly detection model proposed in [16]. Moreover, we conducted a layer ablation study to assess the impact of the local features extracted by Conv1D layer and the spatial features derived by GAT layers on the DDoS attack detection. To this end, we compared CG-GRU with GRU, where only the temporal information extracted by GRU layers is used. We also transplant the Conv1D and GAT layers to LSTM model proposed in [16] to assess their impact on the model's performance.

The results depicted in Figure 31 demonstrate the superiority of CG-GRU model in achieving the highest performance scores compared to all other models. In fact, CG-GRU model exhibits a high sensitivity in identifying anomalous CNF's status while yielding an acceptable Precision of 86.43% and a F1 score of 92.37%. Compared with the LSTM-based model, CG-GRU improves the Precision, Recall and F1 scores by at least 3.96%, 1.56% and 2.98%, respectively. This improvement is attributed to the quality of the learned spatio-temporal features, which allows better estimation of the anomaly threshold. This statement is corroborated by the results of the ablation study. The results reported in Figure 31 show that adding Conv1D and GAT layers allows CG-GRU model to

outperforms the baseline GRU model, increasing the Precision, Recall and F1 scores by at least 2.89%, 1.64% and 2.22%, respectively.

Figure 31. Attack detection performance of CG-GRU [15]

Besides its effectiveness, we evaluated the efficiency of AI-powered EDoS Mitigator in terms of the economic damage repair (EDR), which is measured by the difference in extra CNF replicas induced by application-layer DDoS attack with and without DDoS Mitigator. Figure 32 depicts the number of extra replicas induced by Hulk and Slowloris attacks on a vCDN slice, with and without using the DDoS Mitigator. Note that without DDoS Mitigator, the attack is stopped when the maximum replica count of the video streamer CNF is reached (set to 15 in our experiment). The results show that AI-powered EDoS Mitigator can considerably reduce the economic damage, achieving 89.16% EDR. In the case of Slowloris, the EDR is 100% thanks to the early detection of this attack. It is worth mentioning that the detection times of Hulk and Slowloris attacks are calculated based on the analysis of the testing dataset by CG-GRU model.

Figure 32. Economic damage caused by Hulk (H) and Slowloris (S), with and without the EDoS Mitigator [15]

8.2.4. Future Work and Risks

In the future, we will work on implementing the interfaces of the asset's components to enable their integration with the Horizontal Pod Autoscaling (HPA) of K8s. We are also considering the use of the Service Mesh Istio to collect the performance metrics of the vCDN's CNFs. As a result, this will induce updates to the Monitoring System, and may require retraining the CG-GRU model.

8.3. Security Testing - Digital Twins - DT

8.3.1. Component Architecture

Internet-of-Things includes several physical devices/sensors and systems connected to each other. This means that there is a need to interoperate seamlessly with all actors, i.e., hardware, software. As such, for two actors to interoperate, they need to have a shared understanding of the data exchanged. Achieving a shared understanding is a non-trivial task since a myriad of technologies and protocols, aimed at device communication exist. For instance, in a real-world system, temperature sensors need to measure temperature and send their readings, e.g., a numeric value and its units to another device.

Figure 33. Component Architecture for Smart Meter – Gateway Interaction

This component architecture describes the interaction between a smart meter and a gateway, facilitated by a Digital Twin. The system ensures seamless communication by detecting and resolving expected XML message format mismatches.

The components of the system are:

1. Smart Meter:

- Function: Sends XML messages containing data readings to the gateway.
- Output: XML messages.

2. Gateway:

- Function: Receives XML messages from the smart meter and expects a specific format, including predefined fields and values.
- Input: XML messages from the smart meter.
- Error Handling: Triggers the Dynamic Automated Service Composition process in case of format mismatches.

3. Dynamic Automated Service Composition:

- Trigger: Activated by the gateway upon detection of a format mismatch in the received XML messages.
- Process:
 - a. Document Parsing: Parses the XML messages to identify and classify errors.
 - b. Error Detection and Classification: Determines the nature of the mismatch (e.g., missing fields, incorrect values).
 - c. Service Retrieval: Retrieves appropriate services from corresponding repositories to resolve the detected mismatches.
- Output: Corrected XML messages or error resolution procedures.

4. Service Repositories:

- Function: Store and provide services.
- Integration: Interfaces with the Dynamic Automated Service Composition to supply necessary services based on identified errors.

5. Digital Twin:

- Function: Simulates the entire ecosystem, including the smart meter, and the gateway.
- Purpose: Virtually reconstructs the process to ensure accuracy and efficiency in resolving communication mismatches.

The needed actions in order to address potential format mismatches and ensure accurate data transmission are the following:

1. Message Transmission:

- The smart meter sends an XML message to the gateway.

2. Message Reception and Validation:

- The gateway receives the XML message and validates it against the expected format.
- If the message format matches, the process continues as normal.

3. Mismatch Detection and Trigger:

- If a format mismatch is detected, the gateway triggers the Dynamic Automated Service Composition.

4. Dynamic Automated Service Composition:

- Document Parsing: The XML message is parsed to identify errors.
- Error Classification: Errors are classified to understand the specific mismatch.
- Service Retrieval: Appropriate services are retrieved from the repositories to correct the errors.

5. Error Resolution and Feedback:

- Retrieved services are applied to resolve the detected mismatches.
- Corrected XML messages or feedback for resolution are sent back to the gateway.

6. Digital Twin Simulation:

- The Digital Twin simulates the interactions between the smart meter, the gateway, and the service composition, ensuring a comprehensive virtual reconstruction for validation and optimization.

By employing a Digital Twin and Dynamic Automated Service Composition, the system ensures robust handling of XML message format mismatches, maintaining seamless communication between smart meters and gateways.

8.3.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

In the context of smart meter systems, effective data monitoring is crucial for ensuring accurate and reliable measurements. This section details the implementation of a Digital Twin for a smart meter, which is designed to monitor water flow and associated parameters. Digital Twin is fed virtual data in a .csv format to simulate real-world conditions and facilitate comprehensive data services.

The dataset is retrieved from: [HTTPS://ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/7506076](https://zenodo.org/records/7506076).

Further information on data collection and description of the dataset can be found in section 3 of the original article, which is available at the following DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.3390/JSAN12030046](https://doi.org/10.3390/JSAN12030046).

The .csv files fed into the Digital Twin will include the following parameters:

Time (YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS), Unix time, Flow Rate (m³/h)

By utilizing a Digital Twin fed with virtual data in .csv format, the smart meter system achieves high fidelity in monitoring water flow and associated parameters. This approach enables precise simulation of real-world conditions.

8.3.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The software is currently in the design phase, where we've meticulously planned its architecture, features, and user interface. Development has not yet commenced, but we anticipate moving into that stage soon.

8.3.4. Future Work and Risks

In the following months, the implementation of digital twins will start for both smart meters and gateways, creating virtual replicas that mirror their real-world counterparts. These digital twins will be integrated with dynamic automated service composition system, allowing us to test and optimize various scenarios and configurations. This integration enables leveraging both open-source and custom-developed services seamlessly, enhancing the flexibility and adaptability of our solution.

8.4. Dynamic and Automated Service Composition - DSC

8.4.1. Component Architecture

- A. **Parsing, Detection, and Classification Tool:** This component is responsible for receiving alerts or triggers and then scan the files involved. It detects any mismatches or errors within these files and classifies or identifies the type of problem encountered. Essentially, it analyses the input data to classify the issue.
- B. **Service Search, Composition, Problem Resolution:** Once the issue is classified, this component kicks in. It searches available repositories or databases to find the corresponding services required to resolve the identified problem. If multiple issues are detected, it may call upon multiple services to compose a solution, ensuring that the problem is fully resolved.

Figure 34. DSC Architecture

8.4.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The current implementation of the Dynamic Automated Service Composition (DSC) is tailored for policy translation. It involves monitoring translations from XML (Policies) to JSON (Drivers) formats. A custom service has been developed specifically for this purpose, aimed at restoring policy files or drivers to their default, correct values when discrepancies are detected.

8.4.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

As an example, a policy XML file undergoes translation into JSON format, resulting in what is referred to as a "driver" file. During this translation process, certain fields are transferred, renamed, and reformatted to adhere to the JSON structure. For instance, the field "**sourceAddress**" is transformed into "**srcAddr**" while retaining its original value (e.g., **192.168.0.0**).

Figure 35. Policy XML File Translation to JSON

Initially, a default point of reference is established by parsing both the policy and the result. Text-element pairs are gathered and stored.

```
##### Correct/Common Fields (Filtered to show tag last part) ###
Translated field pairs: destinationAddress ==> dstAddr
Common/Correct value: 0.0.0.0/0

Translated field pairs: action ==> action
Common/Correct value: drop

Translated field pairs: sourceAddress ==> srcAddr
Common/Correct value: 192.168.0.0

Translated field pairs: name ==> name
Common/Correct value: ejemplo1
```

Figure 36. Mismatch Identification and Correction

The parsed results are compared, with the values in this case, considered as defaults. Translation outcomes are then generated for both elements. These results will form a training dataset for classification, where each discrepancy is labelled accordingly.

A malicious attack has the potential to modify existing values, such as the source IP address, remove necessary fields, or introduce new fields within either the *policy* or the *driver*. As an illustration, in this scenario, the `<sourceAddress>` is changed from **192.168.0.0** to **192.160.0.0** to create a discrepancy. Consequently, the altered policy permits an unrecognised source IP.

```
<ITResource id="mapl_9e9dbbdfad5d4ef588fc5ec579f83c59"
orchestrationID="omspl_5b0fd7359a5e40fe92399710c1152ed9">
  <configuration xsi:type="RuleSetConfiguration">
    <capability>
      <Name>Firewall</Name>
    </capability>
    <configurationRule>
      <configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FirewallRuleAction">
        <firewallActionType>DROP</firewallActionType>
      </configurationRuleAction>
      <configurationCondition xsi:type="FirewallConfigurationCondition">
        <isCNF>false</isCNF>
        <ruleParameters>
          <isCNF>false</isCNF>
          <destinationAddress>0.0.0.0</destinationAddress>
          <action>drop</action>
          <sourceAddress>192.160.0.0</sourceAddress>
          <name>ejempl0</name>
        </ruleParameters>
      </configurationCondition>
      <externalData xsi:type="Priority">
        <value>60000</value>
      </externalData>
      <Name>Rule0</Name>
      <isCNF>false</isCNF>
    </configurationRule>
    <Name>ConfS</Name>
  </configuration>
  <enable>Candidates<
    <enabler>firewall</enabler>
  </enableCandidates>
</ITResource>
```

Figure 37. Malicious Attack Modifying Existing sourceAddress Values

Mismatches are detected and identified. A service will then be invoked to revert the altered values back to their original state in the policy. These services can either be *custom-built* or obtained from *relevant repositories*. Various types of discrepancies may exist, including *modified values*, *elements*, *names*, *tags*, and more. Different services tailored to address specific types of discrepancies will be combined (composition) to restore the integrity of the policy documents.

```
##### Detecting altered values #####
-Alert-
Value mismatch for: sourceAddress
Correct value: 192.168.0.0
Detected value: 192.160.0.0
XML value location: ITResourceOrchestration/ITResource/configuration/configurationRule/configurationCondition/ruleParameters/sourceAddress
JSON value location: srcAddr
```

Figure 38. Mismatch Identification

The mismatch has been rectified, and the policy now accurately reflects the correct information.

```
<ns0:capability>
  <ns0:Name>Conf0</ns0:Name>
</ns0:capability>
<ns0:configurationRule>
  <ns0:configurationRuleAction xsi:type="FirewallRuleAction">
    <ns0:firewallActionType>DROP</ns0:firewallActionType>
  </ns0:configurationRuleAction>
  <ns0:configurationCondition xsi:type="FirewallConfigurationCondition">
    <ns0:isCNF>false</ns0:isCNF>
    <ns0:ruleParameters>
      <ns0:isCNF>false</ns0:isCNF>
      <ns0:destinationAddress>0.0.0.0</ns0:destinationAddress>
      <ns0:action>drop</ns0:action>
      <ns0:sourceAddress>192.168.0.0</ns0:sourceAddress>
      <ns0:name>ejemplo1</ns0:name>
    </ns0:ruleParameters>
  </ns0:configurationCondition>
  <ns0:externalData xsi:type="Priority">
    <ns0:value>60000</ns0:value>
  </ns0:externalData>
  <ns0:Name>Conf0</ns0:Name>
  <ns0:isCNF>false</ns0:isCNF>
</ns0:configurationRule>
<ns0:Name>Conf0</ns0:Name>
</ns0:configuration>
<ns0:enablerCandidates>
```

Figure 39. Mismatch Rectification

8.4.4. Future Work and Risks

Parsing and detecting mismatches in the resulting translations has been completed. By the end of July 2024, the dataset will be expanded with additional examples. Support for a wider range of issues (i.e., Gateway-Server mismatches for IoT) will be implemented by the end of May 2024. For example, one provider sends XML messages with data about two outdoor temperature sensors and one consumer expects to receive XML messages with data about one or more temperature sensors. The provider sends, **the temperature value** and **units** for each sensor, whereas the consumer for each sensor must receive the **temperature value**, **units**, and **sensor location**.

Listing 1. Provider sent XML message sample

```
1 <outdoortempsens>
2   <temp1val>18</temp1val>
3   <temp1units>C</temp1units>
4   <temp2val>68</temp2val>
5   <temp2units>F</temp2units>
6 </outdoortempsens>
```

Listing 2. Consumer expected XML message sample

```
1 <temperaturesensors>
2   <ts units="Cels" val="18" lat="38.660781" long="-9.204899"/>
3   <ts units="Fahr" val="68" lat="38.660092" long="-9.204879"/>
4 </temperaturesensors>
```

Figure 40. Provider and Consumer Expected Message Samples

Custom-created or open-source services will be considered by June 2024. Integration with the correlator will be completed by July 2024.

Currently WINGS is discussing with ITAV and OneSource to explore broader possibilities for implementing DSC. OneSource services for messaging, orchestration, metrics, and portals are being considered to aid in and integrate with the ITAV use case.

Regarding the Digital Twin, one potential implementation involves simulating an attack by modifying values or elements, subsequently triggering the DSC.

8.5. AI-driven 6G Response Mitigation

8.5.1. Component Architecture

The AI-driven 6G response mitigation architecture is shown in Figure 42. It takes the input from the AID and takes the counter-mitigation actions as listed in Table 9. Figure 41 shows the component architecture of the AI-driven 6G response mitigator. It takes the input from orchestrator and takes the counter-mitigation actions as listed in Table 9. It uses ensemble machine learning approach. A reward function, action and state space of the network will be used to train and give decisions accordingly.

Figure 41. AI-driven Response-Mitigator functional block

It will initialize two neural networks with the same architecture: Main network and Target network. The reason for using the two networks is that when the same network is calculating the predicted value and the target value, there could be a lot of divergence between these two. Using a target network that has the same architecture as the function approximator but with frozen parameters, leads to more stable training because it keeps the target function fixed (for a while).

8.5.1.1. Inputs for the AI Driven Response Mitigator

The mapping of input states to a (action, q-value pair) will be done by the main and target neural networks. The first layer of the neural network consists of three neurons because its shape matches the state. Every output node is a representation of an action, and it holds the floating-point number q-value for that action. The action with the highest q-value is chosen by the agent. The Bellman equation is utilized to update the q-values in the last layer of the main network.

$$Q(s, a) = (1 - lr) * Q(s, a) + lr * (R(s, s'') + \gamma * \max(Q(s', a')))$$

Where,

$Q(s, a)$ is the Q-value of state s and action a .

lr is the learning rate that controls the impact of new information.

$R(s, s'')$ is the reward received for taking action a in state s .

γ (gamma) is the discount factor that balances immediate and future rewards.

$\max(Q(s', a'))$ is the maximum Q-value over all possible actions in the next state s' .

8.5.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The RM module takes the input from the AID on the initiation of the threat and suggests the mitigation actions to SO (Security Orchestrator) in MSPL (Medium Security Policy Language). The Medium-level security policy language (MSPL) is a security policy language with a medium level of abstraction. It provides in general way a set of actions suitable by the most common applicable security settings (e.g. ALLOW or DENY IP_ADDRESS sentences).

8.5.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

Figure 42. Overall Architecture of the AI Driven 6G Response Mitigation in Context of Rigorous

Figure 43. Examples of security attacks in 5G [17]

A common example of the 5G security attacks mentioned in Figure 43. In the literature response mitigations are highly correlated to the attacks as well as the network architecture that is used for the countermeasures [18] [19] [20] [21] [22]. However considering the literature [18] [23] a table showing the possible counter-mitigation actions have been made to address the vulnerabilities/attacks by using machine learning. This is an initial list of the mitigation actions that have been compiled considering the cases of common attacks on the 5G/6G communication networks and considering how these would be used to train the machine learning-based response mitigation actions. The final list of the counter-mitigation actions would depend on the network topology as well as the attack lists of both user plane attacks and the control plane attacks that will be decided in the future.

Index	Description of the Counter mitigation action
Counter-Mitigation Action 1	Notify the vendor about the incident.
Counter-Mitigation Action 2	Notify the network operator/provider about the incident
Counter-Mitigation Action 3	Block the attacker's access or filter out malicious traffic.
Counter-Mitigation Action 4	Isolate the affected device from the network.
Counter-Mitigation Action 5	Restart or relaunch the infected node.
Counter-Mitigation Action 6	Reconfigure the Virtual Network Function (VNF) to address vulnerabilities.
Counter-Mitigation Action 7	Replace the infected node with a less vulnerable one.
Counter-Mitigation Action 8	Change the network topology to enhance security.
Counter-Mitigation Action 9	Notify the vendor about the incident and block the attacker's access
Counter-Mitigation Action 10	Block the attacker's access and isolate the affected device.
Counter-Mitigation Action 11	Notify the vendor about the incident and isolate the affected device.
Counter-Mitigation Action 12	Notify the vendor, block the attacker's access, and isolate the affected device.
Counter-Mitigation Action 13	Notify the network operator/provider about the incident and block the attacker's access.

Counter-Mitigation Action 14	Notify the network operator/provider about the incident and block the attacker's access.
Counter-Mitigation Action 15	Notify the network operator/provider, block the attacker's access, and isolate the affected device.

Table 9. Proposed Counter Mitigation Actions for AI-enabled Response Mitigation

8.5.4. Future Work and Risks

The RM module would be developed based on the decisions forwarded by the AID agents. As a base case scenario, Table 9 counter-mitigation actions would be used to assess the performance of the RM module. Different scenarios for the initial states would be tested to find the optimum q values for the mitigation actions. After experimentation and testing, the final optimum q -learning network for the RM module will be decided upon.

8.6. Slicing Mitigation Planner Service

Within the scope of the RIGUROUS project, UWS is developing the Slicing Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS). This component is responsible for planning mitigation policies to protect the 5G network against real-time cyber threats. The SMPS determines the appropriate actions and their locations within the data plane where they will be enforced, which can include dropping traffic, redirecting it, mirroring the flow, or the enforcement of a network slice as mitigation solution. The enforcement location is based on predefined logic set by the programmer, such as 'near the source,' 'near the destination,' 'n hops from the source,' or along the 'E2E path.' Administrators can automate these actions through a policy engine, defining different strategies for various types of attacks. This decision-making process is guided by analysing alerts triggered by the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring (NSFM) component.

8.6.1. Component Architecture

The SMPS workflow is depicted in Figure 44. Its functionalities are triggered when a new 5G malicious flow is detected and published to the NSFM Events exchange, at which point the Planner subcomponent of the SMPS consumes the event. This component aims to provide the relevant and sufficient information needed to execute mitigation policies that stop incoming cyberattacks.

The Planner subcomponent employs prescriptive analytics to provide a set of plans based on a proactive threat analysis approach, which includes:

- **What action should be taken to mitigate the attack?** In the context of the RIGUROUS project, the SMPS is configured to select a Network Slicing action to mitigate the attack. It also includes information about the technologies to be used (e.g., Traffic Control, OpenvSwitch, Iptables). This additional information is attached to an object containing all the relevant parameters of the Plan.
- **When should the mitigation action be taken?** Depending on the use case, this can be configured to a specific time, rate, or loop. For example, traffic might be mirrored to a

different network for 10 seconds every hour. However, for this use case, the attack should be mitigated as soon as possible.

- **For how long should the mitigation rules be enforced in the data plane?** The SMPS analyses the cyberattack and determines that the mitigation rule should be enforced indefinitely.
- **Where should the cyberattack be mitigated?** When enforcing mitigation rules, the security engineer should consider critical infrastructure points closer to the source of the incoming threat. However, there are other approaches to achieve this mitigation. For the RIGOUROUS project, the SMPS calculates the specific data path of the flow to collect the End-to-End (E2E) path of all network interfaces where the malicious flow has been detected.

Figure 44. Sequence diagram of the architecture of the UWS SMPS

All this information is encapsulated into a JSON object intended to be a Mitigation Plan. This Plan is sent to the message bus exchange, where it will be consumed by the following components of the closed loop and orchestrated to enforce the mitigation plans at every point along the E2E network data path.

8.6.2. Data Monitoring and Data Services

The SMPS uses network flow information provided by the NSFM component, as depicted in Figure 51. To calculate the End-to-End (E2E) path of the detected flow throughout the entire B5G network infrastructure, the SMPS correlates information from both the flow and topology domains,

supplemented by data from the TIA component shown in Figure 54 and Figure 55. With this combined topological and network flow information, the SMPS can perform prescriptive analytics and generate comprehensive Mitigation Plans for the closed-loop system.

8.6.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

This section covers the development status of the SMPS provided by UWS for WP4 in the RIGUROUS project. The SMPS generates a set of mitigation plans using information about the malicious network flow and real-time monitored B5G network topology. These plans combine strategies executed autonomously to mitigate incoming cyberattacks.

The SMPS utilizes advanced prescriptive analytics functions to execute queries that build the mitigation plans. These queries correlate information from both the flow and topology domains. One such query calculates the E2E path of the malicious flow, providing details about the interfaces where the flow has been detected, the "host" machine, the "flow ID" and "interface ID", and the "flow direction" (ingress or egress). This query output, shown in Figure 45, provides essential information for the SMPS to perform additional queries and build the mitigation plan.

Figure 46 illustrates an example set of plans designed to attach a network flow to an existing network slice, highlighting the multiple parameters provided by the SMPS. Additionally, Figure 47 shows an example of the output log file from the SMPS and the Plan message sent to the message bus exchange. There are two JSON objects, "Resources" and "Plan", each containing a list of objects. For clarity, this has been shortened in this report. The SMPS provides the set of resources associated with the "Plan" (e.g., interfaces, devices, or network flows) and the set of plans to be orchestrated and enforced in the data plane to mitigate the attack.

	Interface	Hostname	FlowId	DevId	sense
1	eth3	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	93690FF5	21A00354	EGRESS
2	eth0	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	7D437342	23A9F542	EGRESS
3	eth7	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	BE43457C	6EBB45FB	INGRESS
4	eth5	EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-1	4B14E8CA	87AEF71A	INGRESS
5	eth6	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	9B3C9F0A	B36282BF	EGRESS
6	eth0	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	4899E2CD	CA96817C	INGRESS
7	eth3	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	491CD2AC	DF6053F9	INGRESS
8	eth7	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	7A57B464	EF54F629	EGRESS

Figure 45. Output example of the execution of the E2E query of the SMPS

	planName	targetType	targetPoint	actionName	planType	sense	FlowId	DevId	stepId	state
1	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	D4BA97BA	F14E4FF5	8	PLANNED
2	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	9F6B84C3	23A9F542	6	PLANNED
3	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	08EE5DC8	E630276A	7	PLANNED
4	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	9B3C9F0A	B36282BF	7	PLANNED
5	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	7A57B464	EF54F629	8	PLANNED
6	FLOW_SAMPLE_D0_SLICING.sql	FLOW_SAMPLE	DEVICE_PORT	ASSOCIATE_FLOW_TO_SLICE	POSITIVE	EGRESS	7D437342	23A9F542	6	PLANNED

Figure 46. Output example of set of Mitigation Plans provided by the SMPS

```
{
  "Resources": [
    {
      "deviceHostName": "CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4",
      "iface": "eth5",
      "programmableTechnology": "TRAFFIC_CONTROL",
      "queueDiscipline": "noqueue",
      "queueLength": "1000",
      "currentTxQueues": 1,
      "deviceResourceId": "5CBB6920",
      "devicePortSpeed": "10000000000",
      "resourceId": "07030AEC",
      "state": "UP",
      "reportedTime": 1717577679380
    }
  ],
  "Plan": [
    {
      "planName": "FLOW_SAMPLE_DO_SLICING.sql",
      "planId": "8B1F8C53",
      "intentTargetResourceId": "07030AEC",
      "intentTargetReferencePointId": "07030AEC",
      "actionName": "CONFIGURE_SLICE_DL",
      "planActivationType": "POSITIVE",
      "orderId": 0,
      "stepId": 1,
      "state": "PLANNED",
      "reportedTime": 1717577887574
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 47. Output example of the SMPS and message sent to the message bus exchange

8.6.4. Future Work and Risks

As next steps, UWS team will be working on different aspects of the development of this component:

- Refinement and optimization of this first functional prototype presented in this deliverable.
- Empirical analysis and validation in a realistic testbed of the performance and capabilities of the component.
- Integration in the RIGOUROUS framework, focusing in the RIGOUROUS use cases and scenarios where this component is relevant.
- Contribute to achieve the RIGOUROUS KPIs and objectives in which the SMPS component is involved.

9 SOAR DRIVEN NETWORK FLOW AND TOPOLOGY MONITORING

9.1. Introduction

This section discusses the innovations and contributions of UWS to the RIGUROUS framework regarding tasks and component related to WP4, particularly in the reactive loop and monitoring of flow and topology domains. A closed control loop in control systems and automation involves continuous self-monitoring and feedback-based adjustments to maintain desired performance. Applied to computer networks, this loop can manage resource allocation based on network load and enhance security by detecting and mitigating potential threats. This approach is akin to the Security Orchestration, Automation, and Response (SOAR) loop, which integrates various security tools, automates tasks, and coordinates software and hardware in B5G security systems for effective threat mitigation.

This functional block serves as the sensing layer of the control loop. It continuously monitors the network from different domains, such as network flow and network devices. Depending on the use case, the analysis of the monitored resources is handled by different software components. Isolating the analysis tasks into separate components offers significant benefits, including the distribution of responsibilities and computational costs. For instance, an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) can act as an analysis tool by generating an alert when it identifies a malicious flow detected by the monitoring tool. This alert includes information on the type of attack detected and the specific network resources affected.

9.2. Network Security Flow Monitoring

This subsection presents a first functional prototype of the Network Security Flow Monitoring (MSFM) RIGUROUS asset as part of the UWS contribution to WP4. A description of the component architecture is provided along with preliminary results gathered in the testbed deployed in UWS premises.

9.2.1. Component Architecture

Figure 48 depicts the component architecture of the NSFM. This component aims to extend the traditional capabilities of current commercial and research NIDS tools, such as Snort. The extensions provide fine-grained metadata about detected malicious flows and enable proper classification of B5G network packets. This allows subsequent closed-loop components to apply mitigation rules to specific malicious flows rather than the entire physical infrastructure.

The logical architecture of this component is comprised by two main subcomponents:

- **NIDS:** The traditional Snort NIDS is configured with rules to detect malicious DDoS attacks. It monitors a single interface in the Service Layer of a B5G network, where the traffic of the 5G Core segment is mirrored. This mirroring allows the Snort NIDS to perform its monitoring tasks without affecting the B5G data plane. When a malicious network flow matches one of

the DDoS Snort detection rules, the NIDS raises an alert. To maximize performance, it writes the alert to a binary file using the Unified2 protocol, which is also used by other NIDS tools like Suricata. The Snort NIDS logs all information about the alert, matched rule, and full network packet. As Snort NIDS does not provide deep packet classification, the following subcomponent enables this capability.

- NextGen NIDS:** This subcomponent extends the traditional NIDS to classify malicious flows in a fine-grained manner, allowing subsequent closed-loop components to perform B5G mitigation. It continuously reads from the Unified2 log file where Snort NIDS logs alerts. Upon raising an alert, NextGen NIDS retrieves it and extracts the full network packet from the metadata. It then uses libpcap libraries for comprehensive packet classification. For different network flow encapsulations, NextGen NIDS extracts the relevant information and creates an object containing the newly classified packet structure. Figure 49 shows an example of a multi-level encapsulation packet structure. The first GTP encapsulation layer belongs to the LTE flow, while the tenant corresponds to isolation protocols like VXLAN, GENEVE, or GRE, enabling 5G multi-tenancy. After classification, the packet is encapsulated in a JSON object with corresponding alert metadata and raised to the system.

Figure 48. Sequence diagram of the architecture of the UWS Network Security Flow Monitoring.

Figure 49. Example of multi-level encapsulated network traffic for B5G networks.

9.2.2. Current Progress and Initial Results

This section covers the current development status of the stated component. Preliminary validation results are illustrated with two figures. First, Figure 50 shows the output log of the Snort NIDS subcomponent of the NSF. For clarity, UWS provided a screenshot of a Unified2 log parsed into JSON format, making the output more human-readable. The JSON consists of two nested objects: "event" and "packet." The "event" object contains metadata and metrics related to the matching detection rule and a brief description of the network flow (e.g., source IP, destination IP, protocol). However, this information is insufficient to halt the specific network flow in a B5G infrastructure, as these IPs represent the physical machines in the 5G Core segment. The "packet" object contains the full malicious network packet detected in the "data" field.

The NextGen NIDS reads the Unified2 log file and extracts the packet object data. Figure 51 displays an output log of the NextGen NIDS, showing the detected network packet already parsed and classified. Note that the new NSF Event, as shown in Figure 51, includes additional relevant fields such as outer source and destination IPs, encapsulation layers, IDs, types, flow direction, MAC addresses, and more. Additionally, a JSON object summarizing the alert is included. This allows for a proper analysis of the NSF Event in subsequent steps of the closed loop.

```
{
  "type": "event",
  "event": {
    "sensor-id": 0,
    "event-id": 125,
    "event-second": 1668685550,
    "event-microsecond": 47407,
    "signature-id": 10000002,
    "generator-id": 1,
    "signature-revision": 0,
    "classification-id": 7,
    "priority": 2,
    "sport-itype": 46679,
    "dport-icode": 4789,
    "protocol": 17,
    "impact-flag": 0,
    "impact": 0,
    "blocked": 0,
    "mpIs-label": null,
    "vlan-id": null,
    "pad2": null,
    "source-ip": "10.2.0.2",
    "destination-ip": "10.2.0.4"
  }
},
{
  "type": "packet",
  "packet": {
    "sensor-id": 0,
    "event-id": 125,
    "event-second": 1668685550,
    "packet-second": 1668685550,
    "packet-microsecond": 47407,
    "linktype": 1,
    "length": 164,
    "data": "QAAAAGACQAAAAGBCBFAACWWhAAEAR0YUKAgACgIABLZXERUAggAACAAAAAKKABAAAAIAVAAAAIAAEIAEUAGR8uEAA0BgpqAoIAAIK"
  }
},
{
  "type": "event",
  "event": {
    "sensor-id": 0,
    "event-id": 126,
    "event-second": 1668685550,
    "event-microsecond": 47407,
    "signature-id": 10000002,
    "generator-id": 1,
    "signature-revision": 0,
    "classification-id": 7,
    "priority": 2,
    "sport-itype": 46679,
    "dport-icode": 4789,
    "protocol": 17,
    "impact-flag": 0,
    "impact": 0,
    "blocked": 0,
    "mpIs-label": null,
    "vlan-id": null,
    "pad2": null,
    "source-ip": "10.2.0.2",
    "destination-ip": "10.2.0.4"
  }
}
```

Figure 50. Example of Unified2 log to JSON file for a DDoS alert raised by Snort.

```
[*] [623] [CONFIG] [1710244649067] [27] [FMAAction] - -- NSFM-ALERT --
[*] [624] [CONFIG] [1710244649067] [27] [FMAAction] - NUMBER OF FLOWS RETURNED BY CLASSIFIER: 3
[*] [625] [CONFIG] [1710244649067] [27] [FMAAction] - LAST FLOW RESOURCE ID: 04004E99
[*] [626] [CONFIG] [1710244649067] [27] [FMAAction] - LAST FLOW ENCAPSULATION LAYER: 2
{
  "Resources": [
    {
      "FlowResourceId": "1E648F07",
      "encapsulationLayer": 2,
      "encapsulationID1": "00000A20",
      "encapsulationID2": "00000002",
      "encapsulationType1": "vxLan",
      "encapsulationType2": "gtp",
      "sense": "INGRESS",
      "outMacSrc": "40:00:00:02:00:01",
      "outMacDst": "40:00:00:02:00:02",
      "srcIP": "101011000000100011011100000010",
      "dstIP": "1010110000001000110111011111110",
      "outSrcIP": "000010100000001000000000000010",
      "outDstIP": "000010100000001000000000000010",
      "L4Proto": "17",
      "tos": "0",
      "srcPort": "10000",
      "dstPort": "80",
      "resourceAbstractionLayer": "2",
      "resourceId": "04004E99",
      "resourceType": "FLOW_SAMPLE",
      "state": "ACTIVE",
      "serviceInstanceResourceId": "369241C8",
      "reportedTime": 1710244649067
    }
  ],
  "Causes": [],
  "Alert": {
    "alertName": "7",
    "alertReasonId": "10000002",
    "alertAssertionType": "NEGATIVE",
    "alertImpact": 2,
    "alertTime": 1668685550047,
    "resourceId": "0A407713",
    "resourceType": "ALERT",
    "state": "FIRED",
    "serviceInstanceResourceId": "369241C8",
    "reportedTime": 1710244649067
  }
}
```

Figure 51. Example output of the executed NSFM with the fine-grained metadata information of the malicious network flow detected.

9.2.3. Future Work and Risks

As future work, UWS team will be focusing on different aspects of the development of this component:

- Refinement and optimization of this first functional prototype presented in this deliverable.
- Empirical analysis and validation in a realistic testbed of the performance and capabilities of the component.
- Integration in the RIGOUROUS framework, focusing in the RIGOUROUS use cases and scenarios where this component is relevant.
- Contribute to achieve the RIGOUROUS KPIs and objectives in which the NSFM component is involved.

9.3. Topology Inventory Agent

This subsection presents the first functional prototype of the Topology Inventory Agent (TIA) RIGOUROUS asset as part of the UWS contribution to WP4. A description of the component architecture is provided, along with preliminary results gathered from the testbed deployed in UWS premises.

9.3.1. Component Architecture

The TIA is a software architectural component of the RIGOUROUS framework in charge of discovering the network topology across the different network segments (RAN, MEC, Transport and Core). It is a distributed sensor allocated alongside the 5G/6G multi-tenant infrastructure. The main purpose of this component is to provide an accurate and up-to-date representation of the network topology including physical and virtual network interfaces, switches, routers and any other network device along with relevant information associated with each network device discovered.

This topological information will be later used by the Slice Manager (SM) and the Slice Mitigation Planner Service (SMPS) to take a decision on where to insert a network slice in the data plane to mitigate a cyber-attack. Therefore, it is important that TIA distributed instances are placed at all network points comprising the data plane where the SM could enforce, control, and orchestrate network slices in real time.

The TIA architecture is composed by three main subcomponents:

- **Topology Collector:** This subcomponent actively monitors the network status in the host where it is deployed. It uses different Linux inventory tools to collect information and create a structure representing the network topology. It is executed periodically to ensure that the topological information is updated in real time.
- **Topology database:** This database is a centralized database containing all the topological information gathered by the different TIA agents distributed along the infrastructure. Its content is periodically updated and populated when any of the Topology Collectors detects

a change in the network topology (e.g., a new network interface or device is discovered, or if a network interface state changes from “up” to “down” or vice versa).

- **Topology Sender:** Whenever a change in the network topology is detected, the Topology Sender sends a JSON message through a RabbitMQ exchange notifying the new network status. By doing so, other RIGOUROUS components requiring the topological information such as the Slice Manager or the Slice Mitigation Planner service are aware of the new topological information.

Figure 52 shows an example of a TIA deployment. It can be observed how the TIA agents, consisting in the Topology Sender and the Topology Collector sub-modules, are distributed throughout the physical machines comprising the data plane. On the other hand, the Topology Database is a centralized subcomponent allocated in a computer instantiated for control and management purposes.

Interface	Type	HostName	MAC	IPv4	NetMask	Speed	MTU	Promiscuous	State
eth3	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0e:00:01	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth1	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:01:00:08	10.1.0.17	16	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth4	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0c:00:03	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth8	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:03:00:02	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth2	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0c:00:01	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth6	LOGICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0e:00:03	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
br-ctf-n20	BRIDGE	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0c:00:01	<null>	<null>	<null>	1500		1 UP
eth7	PHYSICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:10:00:01	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth5	PHYSICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0f:00:01	<null>	<null>	1000000000	1500		0 UP
eth0	PHYSICAL	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:02:00:02	10.2.0.4	16	1000000000	1500		0 UP
br-ctc-n20	BRIDGE	CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4	40:00:00:0c:00:03	<null>	<null>	<null>	1500		1 UP

Figure 52. TIA distributed deployment

9.3.2. Current Progress and Initial Results

The TIA database model contains two types of definitions providing a full description of the network topology:

- **Network interfaces:** It could be a physical network interface, a logical virtualized interface (e.g. tun/tap interfaces), encapsulation or tagging interfaces (e.g. VLAN or VXLAN), and OVS interface, Linux bridges interfaces or even an interface of a virtual machine or LXC/Docker container.
- **Connections:** Describes a connection between two network interfaces. It contains information about the source and destination network interfaces connected and the type of resource.

Figure 53. Example of Topology Inventory Database entries for network interfaces

Figure 53 illustrates an example of network interfaces entries in the topology database. For the sake of clarity, only a few columns with information relevant to the detected and monitored network devices are displayed in the figure:

- **Interface:** the name of the network interface (eth3, br-ctf-n20, etc.).
- **Type:** Type of interface (Physical, logical, Linux bridge interface, OVS interface, etc.).
- **Hostname:** Name of the host (computer) where the network interface has been detected.
- **MAC:** Layer 2 Media Access Control (MAC) Address.
- **IPv4:** If configured, the IPv4 address of the interface.
- **Netmask:** if configured, mask of the IPv4 address.
- **Speed:** Maximum Tx speed in bps configured for the network device.
- **MTU:** Maximum Transmission Unit.
- **State:** State of the network device (UP or DOWN).
- **Promiscuous:** Whether the promiscuous mode is enabled or not in the network device.

Figure 54 and Figure 55 shows an excerpt of the *"Topology update message"* sent by the Topology Sender sub-component to the RabbitMQ exchange as described above. The data sent in the JSON message in Figure 54 are about a virtual network interface (see *"LOGICAL"* as *"devicePortType"*) discovered in a host named *"CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4"*. The JSON is completed with MAC and IPv4 addresses, mask and other interface configuration parameters. On the other hand, Figure 55 shows the same message but with information related to a network interface (see *"iface"* value as *"br-ctf-n20"*) discovered as connected to an OVS virtual switch.

```
"devicePort":  
{  
  "iface": "eth1",  
  "devicePortType": "LOGICAL",  
  "deviceHostName": "CORE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-4",  
  "mac": "40:00:00:01:00:08",  
  "ipv4": "10.1.0.17",  
  "ipv4Mask": "16",  
  "devicePortSpeed": "10000000000",  
  "mtu": "1500",  
  "promiscuous": false,  
  "state": "UP"  
}
```

Figure 54. Topology update message with network interface information

```
"devicePort":  
{  
  "iface": "br-ctf-n20",  
  "devicePortType": "BRIDGE",  
  "deviceHostName": "br-ctf-n20",  
  "mac": "40:00:00:0c:00:01",  
  "portId": "3",  
  "portUuid": "675d8fc0-32d4-4c4e-a7a8-38e87deb11c2",  
  "mtu": "1500",  
  "promiscuous": true,  
  "deviceHostModel": "OVS",  
  "state": "UP"  
}
```

Figure 55. Topology update message with OVS bridge information

9.3.3. Future Work and Risks

As future work, UWS team will be focusing on different aspects of the development of this RIGOUROUS asset:

- Refinement and optimization of this first functional prototype presented in this deliverable.
- Empirical analysis and validation in a realistic 5G testbed of the performance and capabilities of the component.
- Integration in the RIGOUROUS framework, focusing in the RIGOUROUS use cases and scenarios where this component is relevant.
- Contribute to achieve the RIGOUROUS KPIs and objectives in which the TIA component is involved.

10 ROBUST AND PRIVACY PRESERVING AI

10.1. Introduction

This section discusses a different cyber security approach for data security and privacy.

The Federated Learning (FL) framework architecture based on Moving Target Defence (MTD) dynamically changes the attack surface of the system, making it a moving target for potential attackers. Multiple models are used to train the main model with multiple training scripts on devices. This proactive approach increases system security and reduces the risk of successful attacks by constantly changing its configuration and settings. Implementing MTD in the Network environment enables automated, scalable, and flexible defence mechanisms that adapt to evolving threats.

Deploying Encryption-as-a-Service (EaaS) on Kubernetes provides a robust framework for enhancing data security across platforms in RIGOROUS, leveraging real-time encryption, seamless IT integration, and advanced access controls. This involves deploying a Django project on Kubernetes using Docker, which includes key services such as PostgreSQL, Django/Gunicorn, and Nginx for traffic management. The deployment architecture ensures efficient and scalable communications managed through Kubernetes services and pods. This section examines the implementation and how to deploy EaaS for encryption and decryption. EaaS was deployed on the OneSource platform and integrated with their use case (UC). The deployment on OneSource's platform facilitated streamlined operations, ensuring the EaaS solution was effectively synchronized. This integration allowed for a cohesive and secure data environment, enhancing their IT infrastructure's functionality and security.

In parallel, the Privacy-Preserving Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing architecture includes identity and policy management components, secure databases, and anonymization services. The framework uses privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) to minimize re-identification risks. Techniques such as suppression, generalization, K-anonymity, and differential privacy are used to anonymize sensitive information before publishing it to the MISP server, ensuring compliance with privacy policies.

10.2. MTD based Robust AI

To overcome the challenge of reacting to attacks only after they happen, Moving Target Defence (MTD) dynamically adjusts Federated Learning (FL) to distort knowledge of adversary to reduce the chance of model poisoning attack success. The poisoning attacks use the singular-model based operation of FL as a vulnerability. They assume that all clients use the same model as the global model. Then, they emulate poisoned models with the same structure of the global model and inject them in learning process. To make the chance of attack triggering lower, as an initial investigation, training the global (main) model in the FL process by using multiple models is considered as a MTD strategy. In the rest, the architecture, the data management, initial results, and future work are discussed.

Figure 56. Architecture of MTD-based FL

10.2.1.Component Architecture

Figure 56 illustrates the architecture of MTD-based robust FL. Multiple models are used to train the main model, thereby having multiple training scripts at devices. The aim is to train a global model, namely called as master model with a set of slave models. This is done through the components as below:

- **Network State Observation:** Wireless communication status in terms of transmission rates, as well as available computation at devices determine the network status.
- **Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL)-based MTD planner:** At every epoch of learning, the network state is observed, according to which the DRL-based MTD planner decides about the models that should be trained at devices. The models are selected from the set of slave models. Then, the devices are notified with the model they must train. The model selection influences the accuracy and training/transmission time, thereby an appropriate decision is required for MTD plan (model selection). The model selection is performed such that performance of FL in terms of accuracy and recognition time experienced at devices is optimized, while ensuring a robustness confidence. The ratio of the training models at devices which are different than the global model determines the robustness criteria which is kept above a user-defined threshold value. Selecting a different model than the global model at training boosts the FL robustness against model poisoning attack. This is motivated by the observation that model poisoning attacks in the literature apply optimization algorithms to emulate a poisoned model compatible with the global model. To deal with dynamic characteristic of the network and large search space of optimization in model selection, the DRL [24] is adopted and a Neural Network is trained to decide about the MTD plan, while considering the network state variables.
- **Attack Mitigation:** In the case of attack, the adversary that has knowledge about the global model structure, emulates poisoned model(s) compatible with global model and the malicious model(s) will be uploaded on behalf of compromised device(s). After uploading

model parameters, the edge aggregator will perform attack mitigation. For each device, it can be done by comparing the structure of the uploaded model and the planned model for that device. In the case of incompatibility, the uploaded model is malicious and will be removed from the aggregation phase.

- **Aggregation:** For each slave model, the models that have been uploaded with the same structure of that slave model are aggregated at the edge-aggregator, implemented by Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm.
- **Knowledge transfer:** The knowledge is transferred from slave models to the master model. An unsupervised data set is given to each slave model in order to be labelled. Then, the labelled data set is used to train and update the weights of the master model.
- **Broadcasting the Update Results:** For each device, among the slave models, the model with the same structure with the uploaded model will be transmitted to the device. At final epoch of learning the master model is transferred to the devices.

10.2.2.Data Monitoring and Data Services

These categories of data have been utilized for validation:

- **Wireless communication:** For the wireless communication, the settings, including the transmission bandwidth, and transmission power, have been configured according to the 6G settings outlined in the literature (e.g., [25], [26]).
- **Computation:** The computation capabilities have been set according to the MEC capabilities in the literature (e.g., [25]).
- **DDoS data:** We used CICDDoS 2019 data set [27], comprising realistic traffic to abstract the communications for legitimate and DDoS attack traffic through protocols e.g., HTTP, FTP. We have randomly distributed instances composed of UDPLag and SYN DDoS attacks, among devices for training, as well as for the purpose of test. The dataset provides 87 IP flow features e.g., source/destination IP addresses/ports, protocols, flow packet statistics, flag-related information etc., which we utilize for the attack detection.
- **Mobility of Devices:** Mobility traces of vehicles have been generated by SUMO simulator and based on Manhattan mobility model in urban areas [28].

10.2.3.Current Progress and Initial Results

The MTD-based FL has been validated under model poisoning attack in [29]. For validation, we consider a scenario where 10 devices, moving by vehicles, collaborate in detecting Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attack. There is a bidirectional grid environment, where grid lines are bidirectional roads, and two Base Stations (BSs) at the bottom-left and top-right corners of the environment offering MEC capabilities to devices.

A Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) with 32 neurons in the hidden layer is trained as global model to detect DDoS attack. In the rest, GRU with 28 and 32 neurons in the hidden layer are represented with GRU 28 and GRU 32, respectively. The robustness confidence is 0.6. In MTD-based robust FL i.e., MTD-FL, the master model is GRU 32 and the slave models set include GRU 28 and GRU 32. At

each episode, the adversary compromises 3 to 5 random devices and emulates malicious local models of type GRU 32 for updating using the method in [29].

Figure 57 shows the accuracy of DDoS attack detection. The accuracy considerably decreases after poisoning, and this decrease becomes worse at the late epochs of learning due to more involvement of malicious models in the aggregation. MTD-FL-RND deploys random strategy in model selection, while MTD-FL-DRL employs DRL for model selection. MTD-FL-RND has increased the accuracy slightly. MTD-FL-DRL has increased the accuracy considerably and is competitive with the scenario of FL without attack, due to optimization of accuracy in model selection and selecting at least 60% of the local models different than the main model, according to which uploaded malicious models can be detected and mitigated.

Figure 58 shows the recognition time including time for training, transmission, and DDoS attack detection. The recognition time reduces after MTD application with GRU 32 as master. Since, it uses GRU 28 for at least 60% of devices which demands less training and transmission time than GRU 32.

Figure 57. Accuracy gain in MTD-based-FL

Figure 58. Recognition Time in MTD-based FL.

10.2.4.Future Work and Risks

As future work the MTD-based-FL will be evaluated with various attack scenarios. Accordingly, the MTD strategy will be provided to deal with attacks with wider knowledge about devices and FL protocol.

10.3. Encryption-as-a-Service

10.3.1.Component Architecture

A. Deploying EaaS on Kubernetes

Encryption-as-a-Service improves data security across platforms with its advanced architecture. It focuses on real-time encryption, easy IT integration, and improved access controls [30] [31]. In this section, we focused on creating and deploying a Django project on Kubernetes using Docker and related tools (Figure 59). The diagram is an architecture for deploying web applications using Kubernetes, Docker, and continuous integration/continuous deployment (CI/CD).

Figure 59. Deploying a Django project on Kubernetes using Docker

It describes how Nginx serves as a reverse proxy, directing traffic to a Django/Gunicorn web service, with both interacting with a PostgreSQL database. Each component, including the reverse proxy, web service, and database, is encapsulated in Docker containers, defined by Dockerfiles, and orchestrated using Docker Compose with environment configurations managed through .env files. The deployment process on Kubernetes involves creating deployments for each service, ensuring communication between them via Kubernetes services, and managing pods efficiently. This setup exemplifies a robust infrastructure for reliable, scalable web application deployment and management.

To deploy a Django EaaS project in Kubernetes, we need different services. The three main services discussed were:

- Database service (db): This service usually uses PostgreSQL. We looked at how to create and configure it with a Dockerfile. Also, the use of .env files to store sensitive information was explained.
- Web service: This service includes Django and Gunicorn, which acts as a WSGI server. Building the Dockerfile for the service was discussed, including installing dependencies, copying the project code, and setting Gunicorn to listen on port 8000.
- Nginx service: This service acts as a reverse proxy to manage traffic and direct it to the web service. Configured Nginx to listen on port 80 and redirect traffic to the web service.

In the following, the steps to build Docker containers will be reviewed. This includes creating a Dockerfile for each service. For the web service, the Dockerfile includes installing dependencies, copying project files, and setting up Gunicorn. For the Nginx service, the Dockerfile consisted of copying the Nginx config file and setting the executable command. Also, how to build a Docker image using the docker build command and test it with docker run is explained.

Docker Compose is a tool that allows us to manage different Docker services with a single YAML file. We looked at how to define services in Docker Compose and map ports. Also, dependencies between services and settings related to networking and storage are explained. To configure Nginx, we looked at how to create an upstream to direct traffic to the web service. Also discussed are settings for Nginx listening on port 80 and how to configure paths for static and media files. We tested Minikube in a local environment. We looked at setting up Minikube and running YAML files with Kubectl applied. To test the services, we used Curl to send requests to them. Also, how to check the logs with kubectl logs to make sure the services are working correctly was explained.

Each of these services runs as a pod in Kubernetes. In order for different services to communicate with each other, Kubernetes services are used to facilitate access between services. For external access, the Nginx service is usually configured as LoadBalancer or Ingress. In this deployment, we name the Django/Gunicorn service "webservice" to make it recognizable to other services, especially Nginx. This service connects to the PostgreSQL database service to retrieve the data it needs, and Nginx connects to the web service to route HTTP/HTTPS traffic. To deploy these services in Kubernetes, proper YAML files for Secrets, ConfigMaps, Deployments, and Services must be created. Also, in production scenarios, things like logging, monitoring, scaling, and data replication should be considered (Figure 60).

To communicate with the world outside the Kubernetes cluster, clients first connect to Nginx, which acts as an entry point and then routes requests to appropriate internal services, such as the Django/Gunicorn service. Minikube is a platform that allows running a single-node Kubernetes cluster in a local environment, such as a laptop or PC. This tool allows developers and DevOps engineers to quickly install Kubernetes for testing, development, or learning. Minikube includes all the core components of Kubernetes, including Deployments, Services, and ConfigMaps, and is compatible with common tools such as kubectl. In Kubernetes, a cluster may contain one or more nodes. Each node can host multiple pods, and each pod can host one or more containers. Each node has its own resources such as CPU, memory, and storage. When pods are deployed in the cluster, Kubernetes automatically determines which nodes are best suited to run the pods. To check the sufficient resources in the nodes, tools such as kubectl describe nodes and kubectl get pods -o wide are used to monitor the cluster and check how the pods are distributed.

Figure 60. Considering the scenario for deploying the project in K8s

kubectl is the primary tool for Kubernetes cluster management. When using Minikube, kubectl allows us to connect to the cluster, create new resources, and monitor the status of the cluster and pods (Figure 60). We can use containers such as PostgreSQL to create and deploy an SQL database. For example, if we want to have a PostgreSQL version 15, we can call the version associated with this version from Docker Hub. YAML files are commonly used to create and run a database in Kubernetes. These files contain Kubernetes resource definitions for developing and managing pods, deployments, and services. "kubectl apply -f db-deployment.yaml -f db-service.yaml" This command applies the YAML files and creates the required deployment and service. This way, we will deploy one replica of PostgreSQL and a service listening on the specified port (Figure 61).

```
GNU nano 6.2 db.yaml
apiVersion: apps/v1
kind: Deployment
metadata:
  name: db
spec:
  replicas: 1
  selector:
    matchLabels:
      name: db
  template:
    metadata:
      labels:
        name: db
    spec:
      containers:
        - name: db
          image: postgres:15
          ports:
            - containerPort: 5432
          env:
            - name: POSTGRES_USER
              value: "ict"
            - name: POSTGRES_PASSWORD
              value: "1111"
            - name: POSTGRES_DB
              value: "ict"
---
# START Service
apiVersion: v1
kind: Service
metadata:
  name: db
  labels:
```

Figure 61. Considering one replica of PostgreSQL on the specified port

B. Django/Gunicorn Container

Django is a popular high-level web development framework in the Python programming language. This framework has attracted the attention of many web developers due to its Model-View-Controller (MVC) architecture, powerful tools for database management, and a fast and efficient development environment. As discussed in previous sections, Django can run on Kubernetes environments. To deploy Django on Kubernetes, the following is required:

- **Django/Gunicorn Container:**
This container is responsible for running the Django application. Gunicorn is used as a WSGI server to handle requests.
- **Nginx service:**
It handles HTTP and proxy requests to Django/Gunicorn.
- **Database:** such as PostgreSQL that stores application data.
- **Using Secrets for sensitive information:**
Secrets are used in Kubernetes to store sensitive information such as API keys and passwords.
- **Monitoring and Logging:**
Monitoring tools are used to monitor the Django application, and logs are saved to investigate problems and improve performance.

To deploy a Django project to Kubernetes, we first need to create a Docker image for the project. A Docker image contains the project code, dependencies, and settings necessary to run the project. The following describes the steps to build a Dockerfile for the Django project and create a Docker image.

C. Build a Dockerfile for Django

A Dockerfile is a file that defines a set of commands to build a Docker image. This file should specify what images will be used as a base, how dependencies will be installed, and how the project will run. The following example shows a simple Dockerfile for a Django project that uses Gunicorn to run the application (Figure 62). After installing the required modules in the container, we need to ensure that they are also installed correctly on the pods from which the container is built.

images are used for each service and required environment settings are provided through .env and Dockerfile files. The Nginx service acts as a proxy reverser and Gunicorn handles incoming requests through port 8000. Also, the paths related to static and media files are set correctly so that access to these resources is possible. In general, this configuration is similar to the one used in a Kubernetes cluster (Figure 65 and Figure 66).

```
1 upstream ICT {
2     server web:8000;
3 }
4
5 server {
6
7     listen 80;
8
9     location / {
10        proxy_pass http://localhost:8000;
11        proxy_set_header X-Forwarded-For $proxy_add_x_forwarded_for;
12        proxy_set_header Host $host;
13        proxy_redirect off;
14    }
15
16    location /static/ {
17        alias /home/ICT/web/staticfiles;
18    }
19
20 }
21
22 }
```

Figure 65. The details of Django upstream to the web service on port 8000

```
7     volumes:
8         - static_volume:/home/ICT/web/staticfiles
9     expose:
10        - 8000
11     env_file:
12        - ./ICT/ICT/.env.web
13     depends_on:
14        - db
15     db:
16        image: postgres:15
17        volumes:
18            - postgres_data:/var/lib/postgresql/data/
19        env_file:
20            - ./env.db
21     nginx:
22        build: ./nginx
23        volumes:
24            - static_volume:/home/ICT/web/staticfiles
25        ports:
26            - 1337:80
27        depends_on:
28            - web
```

Figure 66. The details of Docker compose up.yml

10.3.2.Data Monitoring and Data Services

Data monitoring and services are critical for maintaining operational integrity and security in deploying Encryption-as-a-Service on Kubernetes. Each service is carefully monitored using tools to track health, performance, and resource usage. Logs from each container are collected and analysed to detect anomalies and troubleshoot problems. Kubernetes' native monitoring capabilities are enhanced with tools like Prometheus and Grafana for metrics collection and visualization. Additionally, Kubernetes' logging capabilities play a vital role in monitoring for auditing access and identifying potential security breaches. PostgreSQL is used as the database service, configured through Dockerfiles and managed using Kubernetes Secrets and ConfigMaps for sensitive information. Data replication, backup, and recovery strategies are implemented to safeguard against data loss and ensure high availability.

In this section, details related to pods, services, and other similar configuration components used in Kubernetes should be provided. There are three main services mentioned here: web service, database service (db), and Nginx. For the database service, which is related to the database, a specific Docker image is introduced and the .env file is used for the environment settings. For the web service, which corresponds to the Django implementation, a Dockerfile is defined in the ICT project folder and configured to run Gunicorn. This Dockerfile is located in a folder called ICT and listens on port 8000 when Gunicorn is running. To serve static and media files, specific paths are provided that are used to access CSS, JavaScript, images, and other static resources. This framework allows us to properly implement and manage web services, databases, and Nginx (Figure 7 and Figure 8). With these settings, we have created a Dockerfile for Nginx that contains the necessary configurations for upstream and routing. The Docker Compose file is defined for the Nginx service and the settings related to port mapping and dependencies are done. These settings allow Nginx to properly connect to the web service and handle incoming traffic. To run Nginx as a standalone service in Docker, we need to create a special Dockerfile for Nginx. Also, to properly configure Nginx, we need to include the appropriate settings in the Nginx config file. These settings include the upstream to direct traffic to the web service and the ports Nginx uses to listen for incoming requests. Then, in Docker Compose, Nginx-related services should be added, and necessary configurations should be done. First, a Dockerfile for Nginx must be created. This file contains the necessary commands to configure and run Nginx. In this Dockerfile, we need to copy the Nginx config file to the container and it will start Nginx. The Nginx config file contains upstream and routing settings. In this file, we must define how Nginx will route incoming traffic to the web service and the ports Nginx will listen on.

In this file, an upstream called `django_upstream` is defined that directs traffic to the web service on port 8000. Nginx itself listens on port 80 and forwards incoming requests to the web service. Also, the paths for static and media files are specified (Figure 67 and Figure 68).

```
1 #####
2 # BUILDER #
3 #####
4
5 # pull official base image
6 FROM python:3.8.10-slim-buster as builder
7
8 # set work directory
9 WORKDIR /usr/src/ICT
10
11 # set environment variables
12 ENV PYTHONDONTWRITEBYTECODE 1
13 ENV PYTHONUNBUFFERED 1
14
15 # install system dependencies
16 RUN apt-get update && apt-get install -y --no-install-recommends gcc
17
18 # lint
19 RUN pip install --upgrade pip
20 RUN pip install flake8==6.0.0
21 COPY . /usr/src/ICT/
22 #RUN flake8 --ignore=E501,F401 .
23
24 # install python dependencies
25 COPY ./requirements.txt .
26 RUN pip wheel --no-cache-dir --no-deps --wheel-dir /usr/src/ICT/wheels -r requirements.txt
```

Figure 67. Managing environment variables creating .env file and having database URLs (b)

CONTAINER ID	IMAGE	COMMAND	CREATED	STATUS
78a76c2051d0	django-on-docker_nginx	"/docker-entrypoint..."	2 minutes ago	Up 2 minutes
8d178f59017d	django-on-docker_web	"/home/ICT/web/entry..."	2 minutes ago	Up 2 minutes
4ec38ef71843	gcr.io/k8s-minikube/kicbase:v0.0.40	"/usr/local/bin/entr..."	7 months ago	Up 4 days
.1:32780->5000/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32779->8443/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32778->32443/tcp	minikube-m03			
21fd7a748c12	gcr.io/k8s-minikube/kicbase:v0.0.40	"/usr/local/bin/entr..."	7 months ago	Up 4 days
.1:32775->5000/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32774->8443/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32773->32443/tcp	minikube-m02			
all31cef6b1e	gcr.io/k8s-minikube/kicbase:v0.0.40	"/usr/local/bin/entr..."	7 months ago	Up 4 days
.1:32770->5000/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32769->8443/tcp, 127.0.0.1:32768->32443/tcp	minikube			

Figure 68. Managing environment variables creating .env file and having database URLs (c)

At this step, we have built a Docker image, deployed the services with Docker Compose, and ensured that the services connect to each other correctly. Also, we will set static variables and test services with curl (Figure 69).

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html>
<head>
  <meta charset='utf-8'>
  <meta http-equiv='X-UA-Compatible' content='IE=edge'>
  <title>EaaS</title>
  <meta name='viewport' content='width=device-width, initial-scale=1'>
  <link rel='stylesheet' type='text/css' media='screen' href="/static/src/css/style.css">
  <script src="/static/src/js/main.js"></script>
</head>
<body>
  <header>
    <a class="logo" href=""> ICTFICIAL Oy</a>
    <ul class="navigation">
      <li><a href=""> Home </a> </li>
      <li><a href="#"> Try it </a></li>
      <li><a href="#"> About Us </a></li>
      <li><a href="#"> Contact</a></li>
    </ul>
    <ul class="login">
      <li><a href="/login/"> Login </a></li>
      <li><a href="/signup/"> Sign Up </a></li>
    </ul>
  </header>
  <div class="container">
    <div class="content-form">
      <h1>
        Encryption As a Service Platform
      </h1>
      <h1>WELCOME !</h1>
      <div class="slgon">
```

Figure 69. The HTTP of the project based on static variables and test services with curl

10.3.3. Current Progress and Initial Results

The deployment process involved setting up Kubernetes services to facilitate communication between the web service, database, and Nginx. Environment configurations were managed through .env files, ensuring sensitive information is securely handled. Testing with Minikube in a local environment confirmed that the deployment works as intended, with services communicating correctly and efficiently handling HTTP/HTTPS traffic. Using kubectl for managing resources and checking logs has been instrumental in verifying the deployment's stability and performance. Initial results are promising, with the deployed system showing robust performance and scalability. The architecture's design ensures that each component is independently scalable, allowing for easy adjustment to varying loads and demands. Implementing monitoring tools like Prometheus and Grafana has enabled effective tracking of system health and performance, providing valuable insights for further optimization.

It was deployed on the OneSource platform and integrated with their UC, further solidifying the system's robustness and seamless integration capabilities. This integration with OneSource's UC platform ensured the EaaS solution was effective and well-integrated, providing a unified approach to data security and communication management.

Also, In our current demo, we have implemented the EaaS and the subscription part to prepare tokens for new clients (Figure 70), and we discussed various topics related to deploying and configuring Django projects on Kubernetes and Docker. First, we discussed the deployment of Django on Kubernetes and the role of the three main services (web, database, and Nginx). The database service was defined with PostgreSQL, the web service with Django/Gunicorn, and the Nginx service to handle HTTP traffic. To build Docker containers, we explained the steps to create a

Dockerfile and the methods of creating a Docker image. The Dockerfile included steps to install dependencies, copy project files, and run the app with Gunicorn. Also, we examined how to configure the Django project using environment files (.env) and methods of managing environment variables. Next, the structure of the Docker Compose file, how to define different services, map ports, and the settings required to connect services were discussed. Also, Nginx configurations and upstream settings, ports, and traffic routing to the web service were explained. Also, we covered setting up Minikube and how to test Kubernetes deployments in a local environment and ran Kubernetes files, tested services with curl, and checked logs to ensure services are working correctly.

The image shows two screenshots of the EaaS web application. The top screenshot is the 'Subscription' form, and the bottom screenshot is the 'My Service' form.

Subscription Form:

- Name: amir
- Method: Cloud Edge
- Encryption: RSA Paillier AES
- Region: Region
- Service Duration in Months: Select your subscription duration (counted by months)
- Submit button

My Service Form:

- Username: amir
- Entrypoint: http://cloud.eaas.usthb/encrypt/
- User Token: eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXVCJ9.eyJpZCI6ImYyZGMyZG91ZDQ1IiwiaWF0IjoiMTY5MjQ1MjQ1LjE1Q8tZxoGQyOsut_PoMdozzwhSu:
- Client Host: amir
- Algorithm: RSA AES
- Key Length: 1024 (dropdown) 128 (dropdown)
- Password:

Figure 70. EaaS and the subscription part to prepare tokens for new clients

10.3.4.Future Work and Risks

Further integration with advanced monitoring and logging tools will be pursued to enhance the system observability. This includes implementing more granular logging and real-time alerts to identify and resolve issues proactively. Enhancing security measures, such as incorporating advanced authentication mechanisms and ensuring compliance with emerging data protection regulations, will also be critical. Additionally, efforts will be made to streamline the CI/CD pipeline to automate testing and deployment processes, reducing the time and effort required to release updates and new features.

Several risks need to be managed as the project progresses. One significant risk is the evolving landscape of cyber threats, which necessitates continuous updates to security protocols and practices to safeguard against potential breaches. The complexity of managing Kubernetes environments, particularly with scaling and ensuring high availability, poses operational risks that require meticulous planning and robust infrastructure management.

10.4. Privacy Preserving CTI Sharing - CTI

10.4.1.Component Architecture

The high-level component architecture, depicted in Figure 71. The asset is composed of an **Identity Management** component for access control of producers and consumers, a **Policy Management Service** for the administration of the privacy policies (received from the SO) that will be applied to the incoming event before its publication, a **Secure Database** so unmodified events can be stored for auditing purposes, the **Anonymizer Service** for the application of the supported Privacy Preserving and Data Mining techniques, and finally the **TIP Proxy** that acts as an intermediary for publication and synchronization of events.

Figure 71. Function architecture of Privacy-preserving CTI Sharing (UMU)

The Anonymizer Service, that represents the core module of this asset, aims to protect the identified sensitive information of an event prior to its publication in the local MISP server. It implements several Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs) that seek to minimize the risks associated with re-identification, such as attribute disclosure and identity disclosure. Below, the list of supported techniques is detailed:

1. Suppression
2. Generalization
3. K-anonymity
4. K-map
5. L-diversity
6. Differential Privacy

The usage of an specific technique can be specified initially by the data owner in the privacy policies. These privacy policies consist of two main files:

- **Privacy policy file:** defines the techniques (PETs) to be applied on a set of attributes of the event that is to be published.
- **Hierarchy policy file:** defines the level of transformations to be applied over the data for each PET specified in the previous privacy policy file.

10.4.2.Data Monitoring and Data Services

For the first asset evaluation, we selected a synthetic fraud transactions dataset generated by the PaySim mobile money simulator. Information for each transaction (origin and destination account identifiers, amount, etc.) is included. This dataset is useful and appropriate for this first analysis since it contains information (e.g., account identifiers) that can be declared as sensitive and need to be protected. Below, a table with each dataset feature name, its description and possible values can be consulted:

Feature name	Description	Values
step	Maps a unit of time in the real world. In this case 1 step is 1 hour of time.	Integer
type	Type of the transaction	String (CASH-IN, CASH-OUT, DEBIT, PAYMENT, TRANSFER)
amount	Amount of the transaction in local currency	Float
nameOrig	Customer who started the transaction (account ID)	String (e.g., "C1234567890")
oldbalanceOrig	Customer's Initial balance before the transaction	Float
newbalanceOrig	Customer's balance after the transaction	Float
nameDest	Recipient who has received the transaction (account ID)	String (e.g., "C9876543210")
oldbalanceDest	Recipient's initial balance before the transaction	Float
newbalanceDest	Recipient's balance after the transaction	Float
isFraud	Flag indicating if the transaction is fraudulent or not	Boolean (1 or 0)

Table 10. Synthetic Fraud Transactions Dataset Features

10.4.3.Current Progress and Initial Results

From the aforementioned dataset, data transformation techniques such as suppression and generalisation for the attributes "nameOrig", "nameDest", "oldbalanceOrig", "newbalanceOrig", "oldbalanceDest", "newbalanceDest", and a data mining technique such as K-anonymity, with k=7 and considering the attributes type and amount as quasi-identifiers, have been applied. The resulting event published in MISP is shown in Figure 72.

The aim is to eliminate the risks associated with de-identification, which arise from the possibility of identifying an individual in one dataset using information available in another dataset. For this

purpose, k-anonymity will make each combination of quasi-identifier records indistinguishable from other k-1 records, in this case (k=7) there will be at least 7 records with equal values for each combination of values of the quasi-identifier attributes.

Date	Org	Category	Type	Value	Tags	Galaxies	Comment	Correlate	Related Events	Feed hits	IDS	Distribution	Sightings	Activity	Actions
2023-05-18				Object name: financial-synthetic								Inherit			
2023-05-18	Other		type: comment	PAYMENT								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		amount: comment	<=100000								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		nameOrig: comment	C13*****								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		oldbalanceOrig: comment	<=100000								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		newbalanceOrig: comment	<=100000								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		nameDest: comment	M13*****								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		oldbalanceDest: comment	<=100000								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		newbalanceDest: comment	<=100000								Inherit	(0/0/0)		
2023-05-18	Other		isFraud: comment	0								Inherit	(0/0/0)		

Figure 72. Example of an anonymized event in MISP web interface

The privacy policy file will list the techniques to be applied, while the hierarchy policy file will list the way in which the attribute values will be transformed, i.e. the transformation techniques to be used by the algorithms in the Privacy-Policy file. In Figure 73 and Figure 74, the privacy policy applied to get the previous anonymised event is shown, while in Figure 75, Figure 76 and Figure 77 the hierarchy policy can be consulted.

For this purpose, hierarchies of types static (for attributes with possible values within a defined range), regex (for attributes with unbounded value domain) and interval (for numeric values) are differentiated. The PET's defined in the Privacy-Policy file must use these hierarchies to transform the data and reach the condition imposed by the selected algorithm.

```
1 {"Privacy-policy": {
2   "creator": "juanfrancisco.martinezg@um.es",
3   "organization": "University Of Murcia",
4   "version": "1.0",
5   "uuid": "64948f82-4e0f-4d3a-9dd3-28edeb747176",
6   "templates": [
7     {
8       "name": "financial-synthetic",
9       "dp": false,
10      "attributes": [
11        {
12          "name": "type",
13          "pets": [
14            {
15              "scheme": "quasi",
16              "metadata": {
17                "l": 0,
18                "c": 0,
19                "level": 0
20              }
21            }
22          ]
23        },
24        {
25          "name": "amount",
26          "pets": [
27            {
28              "scheme": "quasi",
29              "metadata": {
30                "l": 0,
31                "c": 0,
32                "level": 0
33              }
34            }
35          ]
36        },
37        {
38          "name": "nameOrig",
39          "pets": [
40            {
41              "scheme": "suppression",
42              "metadata": {
43                "l": 0,
44                "c": 0,
45                "level": "2"
46              }
47            }
48          ]
49        },
50        {
51          "name": "nameDest",
52          "pets": [
53            {
54              "scheme": "suppression",
55              "metadata": {
56                "l": 0,
57                "c": 0,
58                "level": "2"
59              }
60            }
61          ]
62        },
63        {
64          "name": "oldbalanceOrg",
65          "pets": [
66            {
67              "scheme": "generalization",
68              "metadata": {
69                "l": 0,
70                "c": 0,
71                "level": "2"
72              }
73            }
74          ]
75        }
76      ]
77    }
78  ]
79 }
```

Figure 73. Privacy policy used to anonymize the event showed in Figure 72 (1)

```
63     {
64         "name": "oldbalanceOrig",
65         "pets": [
66             {
67                 "scheme": "generalization",
68                 "metadata": {
69                     "l": 0,
70                     "c": 0,
71                     "level": "2"
72                 }
73             }
74         ]
75     },
76     {
77         "name": "newbalanceOrig",
78         "pets": [
79             {
80                 "scheme": "generalization",
81                 "metadata": {
82                     "l": 0,
83                     "c": 0,
84                     "level": "2"
85                 }
86             }
87         ]
88     },
89     {
90         "name": "oldbalanceDest",
91         "pets": [
92             {
93                 "scheme": "generalization",
94                 "metadata": {
95                     "l": 0,
96                     "c": 0,
97                     "level": "2"
98                 }
99             }
100        ]
101    },
102    {
103        "name": "newbalanceDest",
104        "pets": [
105            {
106                "scheme": "generalization",
107                "metadata": {
108                    "l": 0,
109                    "c": 0,
110                    "level": "2"
111                }
112            }
113        ]
114    }
115 ],
116 "att_aggroupations": [
117     {
118         "att_names": [
119             ""
120         ],
121         "scheme": "",
122         "metadata": {
123             "epsilon": 0,
124             "delta": 0,
125             "sensitivity": 0
126         }
127     }
128 ],
129 "k": 7,
130 "k-anonymity": true
131 }
132 ]
133 }
134 }
```

Figure 74. Privacy policy used to anonymize the event showed in Figure 72 (2)

```
1 {"Hierarchy-policy": {
2   "creator": "juanfran",
3   "organization": "um",
4   "version": "1.0",
5   "uuid": "d660fc23-6275-487a-8201-80392c3d8134",
6   "hierarchy_objects": [
7     {
8       "misp-object-template": "financial-synthetic",
9       "attribute-hierarchies": [
10        {
11          "attribute-name": "type",
12          "attribute-type": "static",
13          "attribute-generalization": [
14            {
15              "generalization": [
16                "CASH_OUT",
17                "DEBIT/CASH-OUT/CASH-IN"
18              ]
19            },
20            {
21              "generalization": [
22                "DEBIT",
23                "DEBIT/CASH-OUT/CASH-IN"
24              ]
25            },
26            {
27              "generalization": [
28                "CASH_IN",
29                "DEBIT/CASH-OUT/CASH-IN"
30              ]
31            },
32            {
33              "generalization": [
34                "PAYMENT",
35                "PAYMENT/TRANSFER"
36              ]
37            },
38            {
39              "generalization": [
40                "TRANSFER",
41                "PAYMENT/TRANSFER"
42              ]
43            }
44          ]
45        },
46        {
47          "attribute-name": "amount",
48          "attribute-type": "interval",
49          "attribute-generalization": [
50            {
51              "interval": [
52                "<15000",
53                "15000-50000",
54                "50001-100000",
55                ">100000"
56              ]
57            },
58            {
59              "interval": [
60                "<15000",
61                "15000-100000",
62                ">100000"
63              ]
64            },
65            {
66              "interval": [
67                "<=100000",
68                ">100000"
69              ]
70            }
71          ]
72        },
73        {
74          "attribute-name": "oldbalance0rq",
```

Figure 75. Hierarchy policy used to anonymize the event showed in Figure 72 (1)

```
74     "attribute-name": "oldbalanceOrig",
75     "attribute-type": "interval",
76     "attribute-generalization": [
77       {
78         "interval": [
79           "<15000",
80           "15000-50000",
81           "50001-100000",
82           ">100000"
83         ]
84       },
85       {
86         "interval": [
87           "<15000",
88           "15000-100000",
89           ">100000"
90         ]
91       },
92       {
93         "interval": [
94           "<=100000",
95           ">100000"
96         ]
97       }
98     ]
99   },
100   {
101     "attribute-name": "newbalanceOrig",
102     "attribute-type": "interval",
103     "attribute-generalization": [
104       {
105         "interval": [
106           "<15000",
107           "15000-50000",
108           "50001-100000",
109           ">100000"
110         ]
111       },
112       {
113         "interval": [
114           "<15000",
115           "15000-100000",
116           ">100000"
117         ]
118       },
119       {
120         "interval": [
121           "<=100000",
122           ">100000"
123         ]
124       }
125     ]
126   },
127   {
128     "attribute-name": "oldbalanceDest",
129     "attribute-type": "interval",
130     "attribute-generalization": [
131       {
132         "interval": [
133           "<15000",
134           "15000-50000",
135           "50001-100000",
136           ">100000"
137         ]
138       },
139       {
140         "interval": [
141           "<15000",
142           "15000-100000",
143           ">100000"
144         ]
145       },
146       {
147         "interval": [
```

Figure 76. Hierarchy policy used to anonymize the event showed in Figure 72 (2)

```
146     {
147     :     "interval": [
148     :         "<=100000",
149     :         ">100000"
150     :     ]
151     }
152 ]
153 },
154 {
155     "attribute-name": "newbalanceDest",
156     "attribute-type": "interval",
157     "attribute-generalization": [
158     {
159         "interval": [
160         :         "<15000",
161         :         "15000-50000",
162         :         "50001-100000",
163         :         ">100000"
164         ]
165     },
166     {
167         "interval": [
168         :         "<15000",
169         :         "15000-100000",
170         :         ">100000"
171         ]
172     },
173     {
174         "interval": [
175         :         "<=100000",
176         :         ">100000"
177         ]
178     }
179 ]
180 },
181 {
182     "attribute-name": "nameOrig",
183     "attribute-type": "regex",
184     "attribute-generalization": [
185     {
186         "regex": [
187         :         "(?<=^.{4})[0-9]+",
188         :         "(?<=^.{3})[0-9]+",
189         :         "(?<=^.{2})[0-9]+"
190         ]
191     }
192 ]
193 },
194 {
195     "attribute-name": "nameDest",
196     "attribute-type": "regex",
197     "attribute-generalization": [
198     {
199         "regex": [
200         :         "(?<=^.{4})[0-9]+",
201         :         "(?<=^.{3})[0-9]+",
202         :         "(?<=^.{2})[0-9]+"
203         ]
204     }
205 ]
206 }
207 ]
208 }
209 ]
210 }
```

Figure 77. Hierarchy policy used to anonymize the event showed in Figure 72 (3)

10.4.4.Future Work and Risks

As future work, we will conduct further experiments so that newly implemented techniques are shown, and not only suppression and generalization. Also, we expect to use RIGOROUS data to better showcase the applicability and usefulness of this asset for the privacy needs of the project regarding CTI, and integrate with other assets and functional blocks so that the process is automated and the asset can be easily accessible and used by those consumer assets.

11 CONCLUSION

The present deliverable has presented an update on the status of the assets that are being developed within the WP4 tasks, as of M18. Specifically, the architecture, current progress, initial results as well as future work and risks, have been put forward respectively for all the WP4 assets.

The AI-Driven Anomaly Detection section has presented the assets that focus on identifying anomalies using novel privacy-preserving federated deep learning techniques, advancing current methods for 5G networks. It includes deep learning algorithms like Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) and Autoencoder for anomaly detection models. The AI-Driven Cognitive Decision Making section detailed assets that leverage anomaly detection outputs to assess threat impact and severity, and recommend mitigation actions. The AI-Driven Security Response-Mitigation part featured tools like the AI-powered EDoS Mitigator and Dynamic Automated Service Composition for addressing application-layer DDoS attacks and IoT communication issues, respectively. The section also included analysis of the AI driven 6G response mitigation tool and Slicing Mitigation Planner Service for network defence. The Network Flow and Topology Monitoring section delved into assets that act as the sensing layer in a SOAR control loop, continuously monitoring network domains and isolating analysis tasks for efficiency. The Robust and Privacy Preserving AI section focused on the functional blocks securing Federated Learning through Moving Target Defence (MTD), Encryption as a Service (EaaS), and Privacy-Preserving Cyber Threat Intelligence (CTI) sharing.

This deliverable should be read alongside D3.2 for details on the Trust Manager and Security Orchestrator functional blocks that interface with the Threat Risk Assessor and AI driven 6G Response Mitigation modules of WP4. Furthermore, WP4's assets will be integrated and tested as part of WP5 tasks and will be demonstrated through the RIGOUROUS's use cases (UCs) which are defined in D2.2 and will be showcased in WP5. Eventually, the final results of WP4 will be reported in D4.3 on M30.

12 REFERENCES

- [1] RIGOUROUS, "D4.1 Design Plan of the AI-driven Anomaly Detection, Decision and Mitigation," <https://umu-projects.inf.um.es/products/files/doceditor.aspx?fileid=10585&action=view>.
- [2] "Industrial Control System (ICS) Cyber Attack Datasets," <https://sites.google.com/a/uah.edu/tommy-morris-uah/ics-data-sets>.
- [3] M. Zolanvari, M. A. Teixeira, L. Gupta, K. M. Khan and R. Jain, "WUSTL-IIOT-2021 Dataset for IIoT Cybersecurity Research," Washington University in St. Louis, USA, October 2021.
- [4] S. Samarakoon, Y. Siriwardhana, P. Porambage, M. Liyanage, S.-Y. Chang, J. Kim and M. Ylianttila, "5G-NIDD: A Comprehensive Network Intrusion Detection Dataset Generated over 5G Wireless Network," arXiv:2212.01298, 2022.
- [5] "NFStream," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfstream.org/>.
- [6] I. Sharafaldin, A. H. Lashkari and A. A. Ghorbani, "Toward Generating a New Intrusion Detection Dataset and Intrusion Traffic Characterization," in *4th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP)*, Portugal, January 2018.
- [7] J. Henriques, A. Gomes and L. Cordeiro, "IoT for Improving First Responders' Situational Awareness and Safety on Federated 5G Testbeds," Jun. 2022.
- [8] "mqtt-stresser," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/inovex/mqtt-stresser>.
- [9] "curl," [Online]. Available: <https://curl.se/>.
- [10] National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), "National Vulnerability Database (NVD)," [Online]. Available: <https://nvd.nist.gov/general>.
- [11] MITRE, "Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.cve.org/>.
- [12] Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST), "Common Vulnerability Scoring System version 3.1 Specification Document," [Online]. Available: <https://www.first.org/cvss/v3.1/specification-document>.
- [13] Forum of Incident Response and Security Teams (FIRST), "Common Vulnerability Scoring System version 4.0 Specification Document," [Online]. Available: <https://www.first.org/cvss/v4.0/specification-document>.
- [14] C. Benzaid, T. Taleb, A. Sami and O. Hireche, "FortisEDoS: A Deep Transfer Learning-empowered Economical Denial of Sustainability Detection Framework for Cloud-Native Network Slicing," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, Sept. 2023.
- [15] C. Benzaid, T. Taleb, A. Sami and O. Hireche, "A Deep Transfer Learning-powered EDoS Detection Mechanism for 5G and Beyond Network Slicing," in *IEEE Globecom'23*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, Dec. 2023.
- [16] "NGINX-to-Prometheus log file exporter," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/martin-helmich/prometheus-nginxlog-exporter>.
- [17] "cadvisor," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/google/cadvisor>.
- [18] "node-exporter," [Online]. Available: https://github.com/prometheus/node_exporter.
- [19] "Open5GS," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/Gradiant/5g-charts>.

- [20] "UERAN-SIM," [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/aligungr/UERANSIM>.
- [21] K. Hundman, V. Constantinou, C. Laporte, I. Colwell and T. Solderstrom, "Detecting Spacecraft Anomalies using LSTMs and Nonparametric Dynamic Thresholding," in *24th ACM SIGKDD Int. Conf. on Knowledge Discovery & Data Mining*, Jul. 2018.
- [22] F. Salahdine, T. Han and N. Zhang, "Security in 5G and beyond recent advances and future challenges," *Secur. Priv.*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. e271, 2023.
- [23] S. A. Bjerre, M. W. K. Blomsterberg and B. Andersen, "5G attacks and countermeasures," in *25th International Symposium on Wireless Personal Multimedia Communications (WPMC), IEEE*, 2022.
- [24] Y. E. Sagduyu, T. Erpek and Y. Shi, "Adversarial machine learning for 5G communications security," *Game Theory Mach. Learn. Cyber Secur.*, pp. 270-288, 2021.
- [25] I. H. Abdulqadder, S. Zhou, D. Zou, I. T. Aziz and S. M. A. Akber, "Multi-layered intrusion detection and prevention in the SDN/NFV enabled cloud of 5G networks using AI-based defense mechanisms," *Comput. Networks*, vol. 179, 2020.
- [26] J. Śliwa and M. Suchański, "Security threats and countermeasures in military 5G systems," in *24th International Microwave and Radar Conference (MIKON), IEEE*, 2022.
- [27] C. Benzaid, M. Boukhalfa and T. Taleb, "Robust self-protection against application-layer (D)DoS attacks in SDN environment," in *IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC), IEEE*, 2020.
- [28] A. K. M. Bahalul Haque, T. Nausheen, A. Al Mahfuj Shaan and S. A. Murad, "Security Attacks and Countermeasures in 5G Enabled Internet of Things," in *5G and Beyond, Springer Nature*, Singapore, 2023.
- [29] V. Mnih et al., "Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning," *Nature*, vol. 518, no. 7540, pp. 529-533, 2015.
- [30] Y. Lu et al., "Low-latency federated learning and blockchain for edge association in digital twin empowered 6g networks," *IEEE Trans. on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 17, no. 7, pp. 5098-5107, 2020.
- [31] S. Kiampisheh and T. Taleb, "Collaborative federated learning for 6g with a deep reinforcement learning based controlling mechanism: A ddos attack detection scenario," *IEEE Trans. on Network and Service Management*, 2024.
- [32] I. Sharafaldin et al., "Developing realistic distributed denial of service attack dataset and taxonomy," in *Conf. on Security Technology*, 2019.
- [33] "Sumo," [Online]. Available: <https://www.eclipse.org/sumo>.
- [34] G. Baruch, M. Baruch and Y. Goldberg, "A little is enough: Circumventing defenses for distributed learning," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [35] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari, T. Taleb, Y. Zhao, B. Yang and C. Benzaid, "Encryption as a Service for IoT: Opportunities, Challenges, and Solutions," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 7525-7558, March, 2024.
- [36] A. Javadpour, F. Ja'fari and T. Taleb, "Encryption as a Service: A Review of Architectures and Taxonomies," in *24th International Conference on Distributed Applications and Interoperable Systems (DAIS 2024)*, 2024.

[37] 3GPP, “System architecture for the 5G system, 3GPP TS 23.501 V15. 3.0,” 2018.

13 ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. System Model

Figure 78. System Model Diagram

system-model.json :

```
{
  "LogEntry": [
    "admin.LogEntry.id",
    "admin.LogEntry.action_time",
    "admin.LogEntry.user",
    "admin.LogEntry.content_type",
    "admin.LogEntry.object_id",
    "admin.LogEntry.object_repr",
    "admin.LogEntry.action_flag",
    "admin.LogEntry.change_message"
  ],
  "Permission": [
    "<ManyToManyRel: auth.group>",
    "<ManyToManyRel: auth.user>",
    "auth.Permission.id",
    "auth.Permission.name",
    "auth.Permission.content_type",
    "auth.Permission.codename"
  ],
  "Group": [
    "<ManyToManyRel: auth.user>",
    "auth.Group.id",
    "auth.Group.name",
    "auth.Group.permissions"
  ],
  "User": [
    "<ManyToOneRel: admin.logentry>",
    "auth.User.id",
    "auth.User.password",
    "auth.User.last_login",
    "auth.User.is_superuser",
    "auth.User.username",
    "auth.User.first_name",
    "auth.User.last_name",
    "auth.User.email",
    "auth.User.is_staff",
    "auth.User.is_active",
    "auth.User.date_joined",
    "auth.User.groups",
    "auth.User.user_permissions"
  ],
  "ContentType": [
    "<ManyToOneRel: admin.logentry>",
    "<ManyToOneRel: auth.permission>",
    "contenttypes.ContentType.id",
    "contenttypes.ContentType.app_label",
    "contenttypes.ContentType.model"
  ],
  "Session": [
    "sessions.Session.session_key",
    "sessions.Session.session_data",
    "sessions.Session.expire_date"
  ],
  "Domain": [
    "<ManyToOneRel: domain.tenant>",
    "<ManyToOneRel: device.device>"
  ]
}
```



```
"<ManyToManyRel: software.enabler>",
"domain.Domain.id",
"domain.Domain.name",
"domain.Domain.description",
"domain.Domain.d_type",
"domain.Domain.creation_date",
"domain.Domain.last_update"
],
"Tenant": [
  "domain.Tenant.id",
  "domain.Tenant.name",
  "domain.Tenant.organization",
  "domain.Tenant.domain",
  "domain.Tenant.creation_date",
  "domain.Tenant.last_update"
],
"Device": [
  "<ManyToOneRel: device.device>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: software.software>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.networkinterface>",
  "device.Device.id",
  "device.Device.name",
  "device.Device.description",
  "device.Device.available",
  "device.Device.virtual",
  "device.Device.device_type",
  "device.Device.model",
  "device.Device.tag",
  "device.Device.flavor",
  "device.Device.host",
  "device.Device.mngmnt_address",
  "device.Device.domain",
  "device.Device.creation_date",
  "device.Device.last_update",
  "device.Device.groups",
  "device.Device.locations"
],
"DeviceGroup": [
  "<ManyToManyRel: device.device>",
  "device.DeviceGroup.id",
  "device.DeviceGroup.name",
  "device.DeviceGroup.description",
  "device.DeviceGroup.creation_date",
  "device.DeviceGroup.last_update"
],
"Flavor": [
  "<ManyToOneRel: device.device>",
  "device.Flavor.id",
  "device.Flavor.name",
  "device.Flavor.cpus",
  "device.Flavor.cpu_freq_GHz",
  "device.Flavor.cpu_threads",
  "device.Flavor.disks",
  "device.Flavor.total_disk_size_GB",
  "device.Flavor.ram_modules",
  "device.Flavor.total_ram_size_GB",
  "device.Flavor.creation_date",
  "device.Flavor.last_update"
```



```
],  
"Location": [  
  "<ManyToManyRel: device.device>",  
  "<ManyToOneRel: device.location>",  
  "device.Location.id",  
  "device.Location.name",  
  "device.Location.latitude",  
  "device.Location.longitude",  
  "device.Location.zone",  
  "device.Location.description",  
  "device.Location.inside_of",  
  "device.Location.creation_date",  
  "device.Location.last_update"  
],  
"Software": [  
  "<ManyToOneRel: software.api>",  
  "<ManyToOneRel: software.credential>",  
  "software.Software.id",  
  "software.Software.name",  
  "software.Software.s_type",  
  "software.Software.device",  
  "software.Software.available",  
  "software.Software.version",  
  "software.Software.role",  
  "software.Software.instance_id",  
  "software.Software.creation_date",  
  "software.Software.last_update",  
  "software.Software.enablers"  
],  
"API": [  
  "software.API.id",  
  "software.API.name",  
  "software.API.description",  
  "software.API.protocol",  
  "software.API.uri",  
  "software.API.controller_api",  
  "software.API.software",  
  "software.API.driver",  
  "software.API.creation_date",  
  "software.API.last_update"  
],  
"Capability": [  
  "<ManyToManyRel: software.enabler>",  
  "software.Capability.id",  
  "software.Capability.name",  
  "software.Capability.creation_date",  
  "software.Capability.last_update"  
],  
"Enabler": [  
  "<ManyToManyRel: software.software>",  
  "software.Enabler.id",  
  "software.Enabler.name",  
  "software.Enabler.creation_date",  
  "software.Enabler.last_update",  
  "software.Enabler.capabilities",  
  "software.Enabler.domains"  
],  
"Credential": [  
  "software.Credential.id",  
  "software.Credential.name",  
  "software.Credential.description",  
  "software.Credential.protocol",  
  "software.Credential.uri",  
  "software.Credential.controller_api",  
  "software.Credential.software",  
  "software.Credential.driver",  
  "software.Credential.creation_date",  
  "software.Credential.last_update"
```



```
"software.Credential.id",
"software.Credential.name",
"software.Credential.software",
"software.Credential.user",
"software.Credential.password",
"software.Credential.creation_date",
"software.Credential.last_update"
],
"NetworkInterface": [
  "<OneToOneRel: network.sixlowpaninterface>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.networkinterfaceinfo>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.connection>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.connection>",
  "network.NetworkInterface.id",
  "network.NetworkInterface.name",
  "network.NetworkInterface.port_id",
  "network.NetworkInterface.virtual",
  "network.NetworkInterface.mngmnt",
  "network.NetworkInterface.device",
  "network.NetworkInterface.status",
  "network.NetworkInterface.mac",
  "network.NetworkInterface.creation_date",
  "network.NetworkInterface.last_update"
],
"SixLoWPANInterface": [
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.networkinterfaceinfo>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.connection>",
  "<ManyToOneRel: network.connection>",
  "network.NetworkInterface.id",
  "network.NetworkInterface.name",
  "network.NetworkInterface.port_id",
  "network.NetworkInterface.virtual",
  "network.NetworkInterface.mngmnt",
  "network.NetworkInterface.device",
  "network.NetworkInterface.status",
  "network.NetworkInterface.mac",
  "network.NetworkInterface.creation_date",
  "network.NetworkInterface.last_update",
  "network.SixLoWPANInterface.networkinterface_ptr",
  "network.SixLoWPANInterface.PANID"
],
"NetworkInterfaceInfo": [
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.id",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.address_type",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.address",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.vlan",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.integer_mask",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.mngmnt",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.network_interface",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.creation_date",
  "network.NetworkInterfaceInfo.last_update"
],
"Connection": [
  "network.Connection.id",
  "network.Connection.mngmnt",
  "network.Connection.virtual",
  "network.Connection.src",
  "network.Connection.dst",
```



```
"network.Connection.status",  
"network.Connection.creation_date",  
"network.Connection.last_update",  
"network.Connection.flows"  
],  
"Flow": [  
  "<ManyToManyRel: network.connection>",  
  "network.Flow.id",  
  "network.Flow.mac_src",  
  "network.Flow.mac_dst",  
  "network.Flow.ip_src",  
  "network.Flow.ip_dst",  
  "network.Flow.proto",  
  "network.Flow.port_src",  
  "network.Flow.port_dst",  
  "network.Flow.creation_date",  
  "network.Flow.last_update"  
]  
}
```